

A Compendium to the Phosphoregulation of Mitosis

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Introduction

The regulation of mitosis is a complex, highly ordered process involving thousands of phosphorylation and dephosphorylation events. Many details about the process are still unknown, however current estimates from large-scale, deep phosphoproteomics analysis suggest that the majority of the proteome gets fully-phosphorylated during mitosis (Olsen et al., 2010). To help in understanding how mitosis is regulated, we selected 88 phospho-events believed to play key roles, and used them to create a tailored visualization (Burgess et al., 2017) based on the 'Minardo' layout, in which time is represented as flowing around a schematic 'circular' cell (Ma et al., 2013). The visualization provides a quick yet comprehensive overview of the events regulating entry, progression and exit from mitosis (Burgess et al., 2017). Each phospho-event is visually linked to its corresponding kinase or phosphatase, adding an additional layer of information. An interactive version is also available (<http://www.cell.com/cell/enhanced/odonoghue2>); here, users can click on each phosphosite to open up a popup that contains a brief description of the event, as well as links to supporting literature in PubMed, related 3D structures in Aquaria (O'Donoghue et al., 2015), and protein sequence information in UniProt (The UniProt Consortium, 2019). Below, in this publication, we have compiled all the text from the 88 popups in the online interactive visualization, with the aim of making this information more easily accessible, as well as acknowledging the contributions of the >200 scientific publications that we used in assembling the visualization. This provides a comprehensive compendium of the major phospho-events currently believed to be essential for mitosis.

1. Late G2, Mitotic Kinase Activation at the Centrosome

1.1. Phosphorylation of AURKA on T-288 by AURKA

T-288 is an auto-phosphorylation site on AURKA. Phosphorylation of this site is proposed to occur by intermolecular auto-phosphorylation of long-lived dimer pairs (Bayliss et al., 2003; Ohashi et al., 2006; Zhang et al., 2012; Zorba et al., 2014). However, recent results with an AURKA FRET biosensor suggest that T-288 auto-phosphorylation can occur through intramolecular mechanisms (Bertolin et al., 2016). Phosphorylation of T-288 on AURKA may also involve nucleophosmin (NPM), which is a strong activator of AURKA at centrosomes, inducing S-89 auto-phosphorylation and AURKA activity independent of T-288 phosphorylation (Reboutier et al., 2012). T-288 phosphorylation is removed by the phosphatase PP6, which interacts with AURKA through BRCA1, when phosphorylated by Chk2 on S-988. AURKA can prevent

PP6 mediated inhibition by phosphorylating BRCA1 on S-308 during mitosis, preventing its binding to AURKA (Ertych et al., 2016).

1.2. Phosphorylation of CDC25B on S-353 by AURKA

CDC25B is phosphorylated on S-353 at centrosomes by AURKA, which is believed to activate CDC25B allowing initial dephosphorylation of centrosomal CDK1 on Y-15. Removal of Y-15 by CDC25B triggers CDK1 activity and the entry to mitosis. Activated CDK1 freely shuttles between the nucleus and cytoplasm (Dutertre et al., 2004; Cazales et al., 2005). The related CDC25A is also phosphorylated by CDK complexes during G2 on S-283, which helps to promote mitotic entry (Mazzolini et al., 2016).

1.3. De-phosphorylation of CDK1 on Y-15 by CDC25B

CDC25B is a dual-specific phosphatase that dephosphorylates CDK1 on Y-15 and T-14 resulting in the activation of a pool of CDK1/cyclin B at centrosomes during G2 (Poon et al., 1996; De Souza, Colin P.C., Ellem & Gabrielli, 2000; Lindqvist et al., 2005). Centrosomal pools of Cyclin A/CDK2 are implicated in activating CDC25B resulting in downstream activation of CDK1 (Mitra & Enders, 2004; De Boer et al., 2008). Additionally, Cyclin A/CDK2 binds and phosphorylates APC/CDC20 during interphase, blocking APC/CDC20 activity, thereby allowing accumulation of Cyclin A2 and B1 and timely mitotic entry (Hein & Nilsson, 2016).

1.4. Phosphorylation of BORA on S-41 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of S-41 by CDK1 (along with S-112 and S-137) blocks BORA degradation, promoting BORA association with PLK1, which is required for subsequent AURKA activation of PLK1 (Thomas et al., 2016). PLK1 activation by AURKA-BORA is required for mitotic entry (Seki et al., 2008), while DNA damage interrupts the interaction between AURKA and BORA thereby resulting in inhibition of PLK1 and G2 arrest (Bruinsma et al., 2017).

1.5. Phosphorylation of PLK1 on T-210 by AURKA

Phosphorylation of PLK1 on T-210 by AURKA-BORA activates PLK1 kinase activity, with small amounts of AURKA-BORA required for continual PLK1 activation during mitosis. This activation appears to function as a bistable switch ensuring robust PLK1 activity once a cell has committed to entering mitosis (Bruinsma et al., 2014). AURKA-BORA activation of PLK1 is also required for recovery from G2 checkpoint arrest (Macûrek et al., 2008).

1.6. Phosphorylation of AURKB on T-232 by AURKB

During late S/early G2 phase the chromosomal passenger complex (CPC), including AURKB, is recruited to pericentromeric heterochromatin regions via INCENP, which binds to HP1. This restricts S-10 phosphorylation on HIST1H3A to centromeric regions (Cooke, Heck & Earnshaw, 1987; Monier, Mouradian & Sullivan, 2007; Nozawa et al., 2010). INCENP is able to partially activate AURKB, resulting in auto-phosphorylation of T-232 (Yasui et al., 2004).

1.7. Phosphorylation of CEP192 on T-44 by PLK1

CEP192 binds AURKA and PLK1 targeting them to centrosomes where they are activated. PLK1 then phosphorylates CEP192 on T-44 and several additional residues creating binding sites for the γ -tubulin ring complex. This phosphorylation may also attract additional pericentriolar material components thereby driving microtubule nucleation, centrosome maturation and mitotic spindle assembly (Joukov, Walter & De Nicolo, 2014).

1.8. Phosphorylation of NDEL1 on S-251 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylates NDEL1 at S-251, which is required for centrosome targeting of TACC3. This phosphorylation is

essential for centrosome separation and maturation during mitotic entry (Mori et al., 2007). AURKA also phosphorylates CPAP on S-467 throughout mitosis, starting from prophase. This phosphorylation is required to ensure that spindle pole integrity is maintained throughout mitosis (Chou et al., 2016).

1.9. Phosphorylation of CCNB1 on S-147 by PLK1

PLK1 phosphorylates S-147 and several additional sites (S-126, S-128, S-133) on cyclin B1 (CCNB1), which block nuclear export of CCNB1, leading to the accumulation CDK1/CCNB1 in the nucleus (Toyoshima-Morimoto et al., 2001; Jackman et al., 2003; Santos et al., 2012). CCNB1 and B2 are both commonly over-expressed in cancer causing aneuploidy by inhibition of separase and AURKA-mediated PLK1 hyperactivation, respectively (Nam & van Deursen, 2014).

2. Prophase, Chromosome Condensation Begins

2.1. Phosphorylation of CDC25C on S-214 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates CDC25C on multiple sites (T-48, T-67, S-122, T-130, S-168, S-214), which blocks the inhibitory S-216 phosphorylation required for 14-3-3 protein binding, thereby allowing CDC25C to activate CDK1 (Bulavin et al., 2003; Bagheri-Yarmand et al., 2010).

2.2. Dephosphorylation of CDK1 on Y-15 by CDC25C

CDC25C removes Y-15 phosphorylation on CDK1, which is required to fully activate CDK1 and maintain the auto-amplification loop during mitosis (Karlsson et al., 1999; Lorca et al., 2010; Trunnell et al., 2011; Potapova et al., 2011).

2.3. Phosphorylation of NCAPD3 on T-1415 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates NCAPD3 on T-1415, creating a consensus polo box domain. PLK1 is recruited to this domain, phosphorylating additional sites on the condensin II complex (Ono et al., 2004; Abe et al., 2011).

2.4. Phosphorylation of CENPA on S-68 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates the histone H3 variant CENPA at S-68 during mitotic entry, preventing CENPA binding to the assembly factor HJURP. CDK1 also phosphorylates M18BP1, which along with HJURP helps restrict CENPA assembly at centromeres to G1 phase (Müller et al., 2014; Stankovic et al., 2017; Pan et al., 2017). Phosphorylation of CENPA at S-68 has been proposed to prevent CENPA loading into centromeric chromatin until late telophase (Yu et al., 2015). However, recent evidence suggests S-68 phosphorylation may not be essential for centromere deposition or function (Fachinetti et al., 2017). CENPA is also phosphorylated on S-7 by AURKA during prophase, which promotes enrichment of AURKB at inner centromeres and correct kinetochore function (Kunitoku et al., 2003). CENPA recruits CENPT, with subsequent phosphorylation of CENPT on T-11, T-85, and S-201 by CDK1 promoting the recruitment of NDC80C and MIS12C, which are members of the KMN outer kinetochore complex (Huis in 't Veld et al., 2016).

2.5. Phosphorylation of CASC5 on T-875 by TTK

T-875 is located in one of the MELT sequences on CASC5 (KNL1), which is a member of the KMN outer kinetochore complex. Phosphorylation of T-875 along with additional sites within the MELT sequences by TTK (Mps1) creates binding sites for BUB1, which then phosphorylates Histone H2A. The BUB1/KNL1 axis ensures highly efficient kinetochore microtubule attachment. T-875 is specifically targeted by PP2A-B56 during spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) silencing (Nijenhuis et al., 2014; Vleugel et al., 2015). PLK1 also phosphorylates KNL1 and TTK, enhancing TTK activity and the recruitment of MAD1/C-MAD2 and BUB3/BUBR1 to kinetochores (Schubert et al., 2015).

2.6. Phosphorylation of ECT2 on T3-73 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylation of ECT2 at T-373 (T-341 human iso2) promotes ECT2 translocation from the nucleus to the cytoplasm and activation of RhoA mediated cell rounding. Phosphorylation at T-373 also inhibits ECT2 activity, which is relieved by binding to RacGAP1 at the membrane and prevents ECT2 relocalisation to mid-zone. CDK1 also phosphorylates ECT2 at T-444, which creates a binding site for PLK1 (Hara et al., 2006; Niiya et al., 2006). CDK1 and AURKA also promote cell rounding during prophase by phosphorylating ARHGEF2 (GEFH1), which prevents RhoA activation before anaphase (Birkenfeld et al., 2007). Finally, CDK1 promotes cell rounding by reducing focal adhesion during mitotic entry directly phosphorylating integrins, focal adhesion kinase (FAK) and paxillin (Yamakita et al., 1999; Robertson et al., 2015).

2.7. Phosphorylation of BUB1 on T-589 by BUB1

BUB1 auto-phosphorylation of T-589 during interphase primes its kinase activity allowing subsequent BUB1 phosphorylation of histone H2A on T-120 at centromeric regions. This promotes BUB1 recruitment of shugoshin (SGO1) and PP2A, which protects cohesin at centromeres until the metaphase-anaphase transition (Asghar et al., 2015).

2.8. Phosphorylation of HIST1H2AI on T-120 by BUB1

T-120 phosphorylation of HIST1H2AI promotes the recruitment of shugoshin (SGO) proteins and creates a binding site for PP2A-B56 to localise to the centromere. This localisation is required to protect centromeric cohesin from removal during prophase (Tang et al., 2004b; Kawashima et al., 2010; Liu, Jia & Yu, 2013; Asghar et al., 2015).

2.9. Phosphorylation of CDCA8 on multiple sites by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates T-106 and a cluster of 6 consensus sites (T-171, T-185, T-189, T-199, T-204 and S-219) in the C-terminal domain of CDCA8 (Borealin). This promotes chromosome passenger complex (CPC) binding to the coiled-coil region of shugoshin (SGO), which is in turn targeted to centromeres by interacting with centromeric nucleosomes only when histone H2A is phosphorylated by BUB1 (Tsukahara, Tanno & Watanabe, 2010).

2.10. Phosphorylation of ESPL1 on S-1126 by CDK1

ESPL1 (separase) is phosphorylated by CDK1 at S-1126, promoting binding between separase and cyclin B1 (CCNB1). This inhibits both separase and CDK1 (Gorr, Boos & Stemmann, 2005). CDK1 also phosphorylates Pin1, which promotes the isomerization of separase at the metaphase-to-anaphase transition, a process that prevents its re-inhibition by residual securin and limits the half-life of separase proteolytic activity to anaphase (Hellmuth et al., 2015).

2.11. Phosphorylation of INCENP on T-892 by AURKB

AURKB binds INCENP partially activating AURKB, allowing subsequent AURKB mediated phosphorylation of INCENP at T-892, which forms part of a conserved Thr-Ser-Ser (TSS) motif near the C-terminus of INCENP. This is followed by the auto-phosphorylation of AURKB on its activation loop, which elicits full kinase activity (Honda, Körner & Nigg, 2003; Yang et al., 2009; Xu et al., 2010).

2.12. Phosphorylation of AURKB on T-232 by AURKB

Auto-phosphorylation on T-232 corresponds to the kinase activation loop (T-loop) of AURKB, which must be phosphorylated to fully activate AURKB kinase (Yasui et al., 2004; Sessa et al., 2005). T-232 is dephosphorylated by PP2A, which binds AURKB through the tumour suppressor protein CYLD (Sun et al., 2010).

2.13. Phosphorylation of H2AFX on S-121 by AURKB

AURKB-mediated phosphorylation of H2AFX at S-121 provides a platform for the activation of AURKB (auto-phosphorylation of T-232). This site contributes to the positive feedback of AURKB activation and is essential for proper chromosome segregation (Shimada et al., 2016).

2.14. Phosphorylation of GSG2 on T-128 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylates GSG2 (Haspin) on T-128 creating a binding site for PLK1, which further phosphorylates GSG2 on its N-terminus, relieving the auto-inhibition of GSG2 activity (Ghenoiu, Wheelock & Funabiki, 2013; Zhou et al., 2014).

2.15. Phosphorylation of GSG2 on multi-sites by PLK1

PLK1 phosphorylates multiple sites (including S-151, S-221 and S-349) on the N-terminus of GSG2 (Haspin), activating GSG2 kinase activity to phosphorylate histone H3 at T-3. Phosphorylation of T-3 is required for the recruitment of AURKB and chromosomal passenger complex (CPC) to chromatin (Ghenoiu, Wheelock & Funabiki, 2013; Zhou et al., 2014).

2.16. Phosphorylation of GSG2 on S-93 by AURKB

AURKB phosphorylates GSG2 (Haspin) *in vitro* on (S-93, S-108, S-143), but may phosphorylate up to 11 sites in total. This phosphorylation helps promote a positive feedback loop involving Haspin and AURKB, which promotes chromosome passenger complex (CPC) accumulation at centromeres and phosphorylation of histone H3 on T-3 (Wang et al., 2011).

2.17. Phosphorylation of PPP1R7 on S-24 by PLK1

Phosphorylation of PPP1R7 (protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 7, also known as SDS22) by PLK1 at S-24, S-27, S-44, S-47 and T-277 strengthens the binding of PPP1R7 to PP1 and inhibits the dephosphorylation of T-232 on AURKB ensuring correct AURKB function at kinetochores (Duan et al., 2016).

2.18. Phosphorylation of CDCA2 on S-591 by CDK1

CDCA2 (Repo-Man) is a protein scaffold that enables phosphatase signaling at mitotic chromosomes. During prophase-prometaphase, CDK1 phosphorylation at S-591 reduces the binding of PP1 to Repo-Man, facilitating the recruitment of PP2A-B56 and centromeric localization of AURKB, which then phosphorylates Repo-Man on S-893. CDK1 also phosphorylates S-400, T-412 and T-419 (Qian et al., 2013; 2015). Loss of CDK1 activity during anaphase results in a switch from PP2A-B56 to PP1 recruitment (Vagnarelli et al., 2011).

2.19. Phosphorylation of MASTL on T-194 by CDK1

The T-194 phosphorylation site is located within a region on MASTL homologous to a kinase activation loop (T-loop). Phosphorylation of T-194 by CDK1 during mitotic entry is required for MASTL kinase activity (Blake-Hodek et al., 2012; Hégarat et al., 2014).

2.20. Phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on T-3 by GSG2

GSG2 phosphorylates HIST1H3A on T-3 facilitating the condensation and resolution of chromatids. T-3 phosphorylation also promotes AURKB and chromosomal passenger complex (CPC) enrichment at centromeres, allowing the phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on S-10 (Dai et al., 2005; Kelly et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2010; Wilkins et al., 2014).

2.21. Phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on S-10 by AURKB

AURKB phosphorylation of HIST1H3A at S-10 is required for the correct condensation of chromosomes (Hsu et al., 2000). This site directs HST2P to deacetylate HIST1H4A at K-16 (HIST1H4A K16). Removing this acetyl group allows neighbouring nucleosomes to bind together, promoting chromosome condensation (Wilkins et al., 2014). Phosphorylation of

HIST1H3A on S10 by AURKB also results in a dissociation of HP1 from chromatin, especially from pericentromeric (arm) regions helping to promote chromosome arm resolution (Hirota et al., 2005; Fischle et al., 2005).

3. Centrosome Separation and Mitotic Spindle Formation**3.1. Phosphorylation of NEK9 on S-869 by CDK1**

CDK1 acts as a priming kinase by phosphorylating NEK9 at S-869. This phosphorylation recruits PLK1, which then phosphorylates additional sites, activating NEK9 (Bertran et al., 2011).

3.2. Phosphorylation of NEK9 on T-210 by PLK1

PLK1 binds to and phosphorylates NEK9 on T-210, a site which corresponds to the kinase activation loop (T-loop) on NEK9 (Bertran et al., 2011). NEK9 phosphorylates several downstream targets including NEDD1 (S-377), which drives NEDD1 and γ -tubulin recruitment to the centrosome (Sdelci et al., 2012). In addition, the C-terminus of NEK9 is able to bind to and activate NEK7 by releasing the auto-inhibitory effects of Y-97 phosphorylation on NEK7, a process that is independent of NEK9 kinase activity (Haq et al., 2015). NEK9 plays critical roles in regulating centrosome separation and spindle formation, with loss of NEK9 inducing severe mitotic defects (Kaneta & Ullrich, 2013), which can block the proliferation of p53 null cancer cells (Kurioka et al., 2014).

3.3. Phosphorylation of KIF11 on S-1033 by NEK9

In human cells, NEK9 activates NEK6/7 which then phosphorylates KIF11 (EG5) on S-1033 promoting its localization to centrosomes, where it is later required for driving centrosome separation. KIF11 is also phosphorylated by CDK1 at T-926 (Blangy et al., 1995; Smith et al., 2011; Bertran et al., 2011). The phosphatase PTEN negatively regulates phosphorylation of KIF11 (EG5) during mitosis, with loss of PTEN resulting in hyper-phosphorylation of EG5 preventing its recruitment to the mitotic spindle, leading to short, aberrant mitotic spindles and chromosome segregation defects (He et al., 2016).

3.4. Phosphorylation of NEDD1 on S-377 by NEK9

NEK9 phosphorylates NEDD1 on S-377 driving it and γ -tubulin to the centrosome, where they are necessary for correct maturation of centrioles and nucleation of microtubules (Gomez-Ferrera et al., 2012; Sdelci et al., 2012). NEK9 binds to and activates NEK7 kinase (Haq et al., 2015) promoting recruitment of pericentriolar material (PCM) proteins required for correct centriole duplication and spindle pole formation (Kim, Kim & Rhee, 2011). In response to DNA damage during mitosis, NEK7 interacts with and phosphorylates TRF1 on S-114, stabilizing TRF1 at telomeres, thereby protecting them from further damage (Tan et al., 2017).

3.5. Phosphorylation of STK3 on S-15 by PLK1

STK3 (serine/threonine-protein kinase 3, also known as MST2) phosphorylates Nek2A kinase at S-15 with the assistance of the scaffold protein hSav1. This phosphorylation is crucial for the formation of the hSav1-NEK2A-STK3 complexes and the targeting of phosphorylated NEK2A to centrosomes (Mardin et al., 2011). NEK2 then phosphorylates C-Nap1 on multiple sites, which perturbs both oligomerization and CEP135 interaction, promoting centrosome disjunction at the onset of mitosis (Hardy et al., 2014).

4. Nuclear Envelope Breakdown and Inhibition of Phosphatase Activity

4.1. Phosphorylation of PP1 on T-320 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of T-320 by CDK1 inhibits PP1 phosphatase activity. This site is auto-dephosphorylated by PP1 during early anaphase (Wu et al., 2009; Grallert et al., 2015).

4.2. Phosphorylation of NPC on multi-sites by CDK1

The nuclear pore complex (NPC) is made up of around 1000 different subunits. Multiple nuclear pore proteins (NUPs) are phosphorylated by CDK1 and additional kinases, which trigger NPC disassembly (De Souza, Colin P.C. et al., 2004). Examples include NUP50 (S-221) (Kosako et al., 2009), NUP98 (T-548, T-553, S-653, T-670, reported as T-529, T-539, S-595, S-623 by Laurell et al.) (Laurell et al., 2011) and NUP210 (S-1881, reported as S-1880 by Favreau et al.) (Favreau et al., 1996). Summary of NPC breakdown reviewed by (Smoyer & Jaspersen, 2014; Álvarez-Fernández & Malumbres, 2014).

4.3. Phosphorylation of MASTL on S-875 by MASTL

The C-terminal S-875 phosphorylation of MASTL is a possible auto-phosphorylation site (Blake-Hodek et al., 2012) required for full activation of MASTL kinase activity (Vigneron et al., 2011). MASTL activity along with CDK1 is required for CRM1 mediated nuclear export of MASTL just prior to nuclear envelope breakdown (Wang et al., 2013; Álvarez-Fernández et al., 2013).

4.4. Phosphorylation of ENSA on S-67 by MASTL

Phosphorylation of ENSA at S-67 and the related protein Arpp-19 at S-62 by MASTL significantly increases their affinity for PP2A-B55, where they act as 'unfair' competitive inhibitors by occupying the active site of the PP2A-B55 complex (Gharbi-Ayachi et al., 2010; Mochida et al., 2010; Williams et al., 2014; Mochida, 2014). In starfish oocytes, Arpp-19 is phosphorylated on S-106 by MASTL and S-69 by CDK1, with the latter creating a novel bypass mechanism that is sufficient for CDK1-cyclin B autoregulatory activation (Okumura et al., 2014). Finally, the PP2A-B55/MASTL/ENSA pathway in combination with CDK1 is both necessary and sufficient for creating the bistable switch-like phosphorylations required for mitotic entry (Mochida et al., 2016).

4.5. Phosphorylation of LMNB1 on S-23 by CDK1

Lamin B1 is phosphorylated on S-23 by CDK1 and several additional sites with the aid of PKC. These phosphorylations help drive nuclear envelope disassembly during nuclear envelope breakdown, with complete disassembly occurring by metaphase (Mall et al., 2012).

5. Prometaphase and The Spindle Assembly Checkpoint

5.1. Phosphorylation of HIST1H3A on T-118 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylates HIST1H3A (Histone H3) on T-118 at pericentromeres and chromosome arms during prophase but is lost upon chromosome alignment. This phosphorylation is suggested to occlude cohesin and condensin complexes from the DNA, giving the condensed chromatid increased conformational flexibility that is required for microtubule attachment (Wike et al., 2016).

5.2. Phosphorylation of CDCA5 on T-159 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of CDCA5 (Sororin) at T-159 by either CDK1 or PLK1 destabilizes the interaction between PDS5A and Sororin. Removal of Sororin from cohesin complexes allows WAPL to bind PDS5A, this exchange of proteins promotes the removal of

cohesin, specifically from the chromosome axes during prophase (Nishiyama et al., 2013; Liu, Jia & Yu, 2013).

5.3. Phosphorylation of CASC5 on S-24 by AURKB

CASC5 (KNL1) phosphorylation on S-24 by AURKB inhibits the binding of PP1 to the kinetochore. This ensures that the spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) signal is not silenced prematurely (Welburn et al., 2010; Nijenhuis et al., 2014). AURKB also phosphorylates Mis12C (Kim & Yu, 2015), Dam1 and Ndc80 (Kalantzaki et al., 2015).

5.4. Phosphorylation of CDC20 on S-153 by BUB1

BUB1 directly phosphorylates CDC20 at S-153, providing a scaffold for subsequent PLK1-mediated phosphorylation of CDC20 at S-92, with both phosphorylation events required for efficient inhibition of CDC20 (APC/C-CDC20) in vitro and correct checkpoint signalling in human cells (Tang et al., 2004a; Jia, Li & Yu, 2016).

5.5. Phosphorylation of BUB1 on T-609 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of T-609 by CDK1 localizes BUB1 to the kinetochore and creates a polo-binding domain (PBD), which recruits PLK1. BUB1 acts as a scaffold allowing PLK1 to phosphorylate CDC20, this is one of 2 pathways used to inhibit CDC20 (APC/C-CDC20) function prior to mitotic exit (Qi, Tang & Yu, 2006; Jia, Li & Yu, 2016).

5.6. Phosphorylation of CDC20 on S-92 by PLK1

BUB1 and PLK1 act in parallel to directly inhibit CDC20 (APC/C-CDC20) function (Jia, Li & Yu, 2016). S-92 phosphorylation by PLK1 prevents delivery of the E2 ubiquitin-activating enzyme Ube2S to the APC/C. Removal of S-92 by PP2A-B56 stabilizes kinetochore-microtubule attachments and shuts off the spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) (Craney et al., 2016).

5.7. Phosphorylation of BUB1B on S-676 by PLK1

Phosphorylation of BUB1B (BUBR1) on T-620 by CDK1 triggers the recruitment of PLK1, which further phosphorylates BUBR1 at S-676. This promotes stability of kinetochore-microtubule (KT-MT) interactions, timely mitotic progression, and chromosome alignment at the metaphase plate (Elowe et al., 2007; Lera et al., 2016). Efficient recruitment of PLK1 to kinetochores during prometaphase is dependent on NCAPG2, a component of the condensin II complex (Kim et al., 2014b).

5.8. Phosphorylation of BUB1 on S-670 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of S-670 on BUB1B (BUBR1) by CDK1 is important for microtubule-kinetochore attachment sensing (Elowe et al., 2009). Specifically, S-670 phosphorylation recruits PP2A-B56 phosphatase to improperly attached kinetochores where it counteracts AURKB kinase (Kruse et al., 2013; Nijenhuis et al., 2014). S-670 remains phosphorylated during early mitotic exit (McCloy et al., 2015). BUBR1 in conjunction with MAD2, BUB3 and CDC20 forms the Mitotic Checkpoint Complex (MCC), which is essential for spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) function. BUBR1 contains two conserved ABBA motifs that bind and help rapidly inhibit active APC/C-CDC20 (Di Fiore et al., 2016).

5.9. Phosphorylation of STAG2 on S-1224 by PLK1

Phosphorylation of STAG2 (cohesin subunit SA-2) at S-1224 by PLK1 promotes the dissociation of cohesin II from the chromatin arms during prophase and prometaphase (Hauf et al., 2005).

5.10. Phosphorylation of AURKB on S-331 by CHK1

CHK1 phosphorylates AURKB at S-331 to ensure full AURKB kinase activity during prometaphase (Petsalaki et al., 2011).

6. Attachment, Correction and Alignment of Chromosomes by the Mitotic Spindle

6.1. Phosphorylation of KIF18A on S-684 by CDK1

KIF18A is phosphorylated by CDK1 at S-674 and S-684, which facilitates chromosome movements during prometaphase/early metaphase (Häfner et al., 2014).

6.2. Dephosphorylation of AURKA on T-288 by PP1

AURKA is dephosphorylated on T-288 when localized at mitotic spindles, most likely by PP1 which removes this site in vitro (Walter et al., 2000; Satinover et al., 2004). However, binding of TPX2 to dephosphorylated AURKA is sufficient to re-activate AURKA kinase activity (Dodson & Bayliss, 2012; Zorba et al., 2014).

6.3. Phosphorylation of TACC3 on S-558 by AURKA

Phosphorylation of TACC3 on S-558 by AURKA is required for its spindle localization (LeRoy et al., 2007). AURKA-dependent control of the TACC3/ch-TOG/clathrin axis is proposed to control spindle length, stability and speed of spindle formation (Lin, Hu & Shih, 2010; Burgess et al., 2015). AURKA also phosphorylates several other important regulators of mitotic spindle assembly including GM130 (Wei et al., 2015), NUSAP1, and MAP7 (Sardon et al., 2010).

6.4. Phosphorylation of MAPRE3 on S-176 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylation of the microtubule end binding protein MAPRE3 (EB3) at S-176 triggers disruption of the EB3-SIAH-1 complex, resulting in EB3 stabilization during mitosis (Ban et al., 2009). Additionally, the related EB1 and EB2 proteins are also phosphorylated by AURKB and CDK1, with these phosphorylations critical for correct temporal regulation of EB1/2. Together phosphorylations of the EB family regulate microtubule binding, kinetochore-microtubule dynamics, and spindle orientation (Ferreira et al., 2013; Iimori et al., 2016). AURKA also phosphorylates NUMA on S-1969, which is regulates the spindle orientation and positioning functions of NUMA during metaphase (Gallini et al., 2016).

6.5. Phosphorylation of TPX2 on T-369 by MAPK

The T-369 site on TPX2 is a consensus motif for and potentially phosphorylated by CDK1/MAPK (Wittmann et al., 2000; McCloy et al., 2015; Petrone et al., 2016). TPX2 plays important roles in regulating mitotic spindle length and microtubule flux. Rapid dephosphorylation of T-369 by PP2A-B55 during early mitotic exit is required to release importin- α from TPX2, which subsequently allows TPX2 to localize to the central-spindle. Failure to dephosphorylate T-369 results in aberrant nuclear import (Cundell et al., 2016).

6.6. Phosphorylation of INCENP on T-59 by CDK1

CDK1 phosphorylation of INCENP at T-59 is required for PLK1 recruitment to kinetochores during prometaphase (Goto et al., 2006) with the PLK1/AURKB/INCENP complex playing crucial roles in the regulation of chromosomal attachment to the mitotic spindle (Carmena et al., 2012). CDK1 phosphorylation of INCENP is also important for preventing binding with KIF20A (Mklp2), and thereby restricting relocalization of the chromosome passenger complex (CPC) to the central-spindle in anaphase (Hümmer & Mayer, 2009; Vázquez-Novelle & Petronczki, 2010; Kitagawa et al., 2014). CDK1 also phosphorylates 6 sites (T-478, S481, T507, T524, S798, T807) within the C-Terminal SAH domain of INCENP. These phosphorylations disrupt MT-binding and promote SAC silencing (Wheelock et al., 2017).

6.7. Phosphorylation of TPX2 on T-72 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of TPX2 at T-72 by CDK1 negatively regulates TPX2 association with the mitotic spindle, preventing over-activation of AURKA at the spindle, which can cause abnormally elongated spindles, likely due to increased KIF11 (EG5) activity (Shim et al., 2015).

6.8. Phosphorylation of BIRC5 on T-34 by CDK1

BIRC5 (Survivin) is a component of the chromosomal passenger complex (CPC), which includes AURKB. BIRC5 is required for sustained spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) arrest in response to tension loss (Lens et al., 2003). Phosphorylation at T-34 by CDK1 (Fortugno et al., 2002) blocks caspase-9 mediated mitotic cell death (O'Connor et al., 2000). During a prolonged mitotic arrest, CDK1 also phosphorylates XIAP on S-40 and MCL-1 on T-92, blocking their anti-apoptotic functions and priming cells for mitotic cell death (Harley et al., 2010; Hou, Allan & Clarke, 2017).

6.9. Phosphorylation of CDCA8 on T-230 by TTK

CDCA8 (Borealin), is a member of the chromosome passenger complex (CPC) that regulates the AURKB. CDCA8 is directly phosphorylated by TTK (Mps1) on T-230 activating AURKB during error correction and chromosome alignment (Jelluma et al., 2008; Bourhis et al., 2009). Dimerization of CDCA8 is also important for correct CPC and spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) functioning (Bekier et al., 2015).

6.10. Phosphorylation of KIF2C on T-95 by AURKB

AURKB phosphorylates T-95 on KIF2C (MCAK), simultaneously localizing KIF2C to the centromere, and inhibiting its microtubule depolymerizing activity. However, PLK1 phosphorylation of S-715 on KIF2C balances AURKB inhibition. This crucial balance between inhibition and activation is essential to allow KIF2C activity to correct improper kinetochore-microtubule attachments (Andrews et al., 2004; Shao et al., 2015).

6.11. Phosphorylation of PRC1 on T-481 by CDK1

Phosphorylation of the non-motor protein PRC1 at T-481 (and T-470) by CDK1 during prometaphase and metaphase, negatively regulates PLK1 binding, preventing the localization of PLK1 to the spindle microtubules. These CDK1 phosphorylations are critical to maintain mitotic progression and spindle bipolarity prior to anaphase onset (Neef et al., 2007; Cundell et al., 2013). PRC1 modulates correct spindle formation by binding to and blocking RacGAP1 inhibition of CDC42, which is required for mitotic spindle formation (Ban et al., 2004). In addition, during metaphase PRC1 acts as a 'bridging fiber' linking non-kinetochore microtubules with the outermost sister kinetochore fibers (k-fibers) to help balance inter kinetochore tension (Kajtez et al., 2016; Polak et al., 2017).

7. The Metaphase to Anaphase Transition

7.1. Phosphorylation of APC1 on S-313 by CDK1

CDK1 is recruited to hyper-phosphorylated APC3 where it phosphorylates the associated APC1 at S-313 (S-314 in *X. laevis*), and several additional sites within the N-terminal loop region (S-317, S-334, S-341, S-355, S-377, S-386, which correspond to S-318, S-335, S-344, S-358, S-380 and S-389 in *X. laevis*). These phosphorylations promote the loading of CDC20 into the APC/C, thereby activating its ubiquitylation ligase activity required for the degradation of mitotic substrates such as cyclin B1 (CCNB1), which results in a reduction in CDK1 activity (Zhang et al., 2016; Qiao et al., 2016; Fujimitsu, Grimaldi & Yamano, 2016).

7.2. Phosphorylation of KIF18A on S-684 by PP1

Dephosphorylation of KIF18A at S-684 by PP1 during metaphase, results in metaphase plate thinning, and reduces the oscillatory movements of chromosomes (Häfner et al., 2014).

7.3. Phosphorylation of CLASP2 on S-1034 by PLK1

CLASP2 is phosphorylated by CDK1 on S1013, recruiting PLK1, which then phosphorylates S-1034 on human CLASP2. This helps to stabilize kinetochore-microtubule attachments, maintain spindle bipolarity and align chromosomes at the metaphase plate. Note that Maia et al. report the S-1013 site as S-1234 and S-1034 as S-1255 (Maia et al., 2012). CLASP2 is also phosphorylated by GSK3 during mitosis, this phosphorylation inhibits the MT-binding activity of CLASP2 α , thereby weakening kinetochore-microtubule (KT-MT) interactions. GSK3 mediated phosphorylations are proposed to help spatially and temporally control KT-MT interactions thereby ensuring correct chromosome segregation (Pemble et al., 2017).

7.4. Phosphorylation of TPX2 on S-121 by AURKA

AURKA phosphorylation of TPX2 at S-121 during metaphase is necessary for maintaining correct spindle length after the spindle reaches its steady state during metaphase (Fu et al., 2015).

7.5. Phosphorylation of RAD21 on S-454 by PLK1

RAD21 (SCC1 homolog) is a cleavable component of the cohesin complex. Phosphorylation of RAD21 at S-454 by PLK1, primes the adjacent R-450 site for cleavage by ESPL1 (separase). Cohesin cleavage dissolves the connection between sister chromatids, allowing chromosome segregation in anaphase (Alexandru et al., 2001; Hauf et al., 2005; Agircan & Schiebel, 2014; Lin, Luo & Yu, 2016).

7.6. Dephosphorylation of CASC5 on S-24 by PP2A-B56

CASC5 (KNL1) is dephosphorylated on S-24 by PP2A-B56, which reveals an RVSF motif, a known PP1 consensus binding site. This site recruits PP1-gamma to the kinetochore, where it promotes the disassembly of the KNL1/BUB1 complex (Welburn et al., 2010; Nijenhuis et al., 2014). PP1 is also recruited to kinetochores during metaphase by the spindle- and kinetochore-associated (Ska) complex. The role of PP1 at kinetochores is to promote anaphase progression by silencing SAC kinase signalling (Sivakumar et al., 2016).

7.7. Auto-dephosphorylation of PP1 on T-320

PP1 auto-dephosphorylates itself at T-320 as CDK1 activity begins to drop during late metaphase, concomitant with cyclin B degradation, resulting in an increase in PP1 phosphatase activity (Wu et al., 2009; Grallert et al., 2015).

7.8. Dephosphorylation of MASTL on multi-sites by PP1

MASTL is rapidly dephosphorylated by PP1 as cells exit mitosis (M-A transition) on CDK1-directed threonine sites (likely T-194, T-207, T-741) (Hégarat et al., 2014; Rogers et al., 2016) and on S-875 (in *X. laevis*) (Heim, Konietzny & Mayer, 2015; Ma et al., 2016). FCP1 has also been implicated in dephosphorylation of MASTL during mitotic exit (DellaMonica et al., 2015). Inactivation of MASTL allows subsequent reactivation of PP2A-B55, which in turn likely completes the dephosphorylation and inactivation of MASTL during mitotic exit. Loss of MASTL function results in the rapid dephosphorylation of TTK (Mps1), by PP2A-B55, which deactivates TTK kinase activity and silences the spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) (Diril et al., 2016).

7.9. Dephosphorylation of HIST1H3A on T-3 by PP1

PP1 initiates the decondensation of the mitotic chromatin by the dephosphorylation of T-3 on HIST1H3A (Histone H3), which

may also help AURKB to re-localize to the central-spindle during mitotic exit (Qian et al., 2011; Afonso et al., 2014). Lagging or misaligned chromosomes are rapidly phosphorylated on S-31 of Histone H3.3 during anaphase, which persists into G1, triggering a p53 dependent response that blocks proliferation of aberrantly divided cells (Hinchcliffe et al., 2016).

7.10. Dephosphorylation of CASC5 on T-875 by PP1

The T-875 phosphorylation site on CASC5 (KNL1) is located within one of the ~19 MELT sequences used by BUB1 to bind KNL1. Dephosphorylation of T-875 and the surrounding MELT sequences disassembles the mitotic checkpoint complex (MCC) and turns off spindle assembly checkpoint (SAC) signalling (Nijenhuis et al., 2014; Vleugel et al., 2015).

7.11. Dephosphorylation of CDC20 on S-41 by PP2A-B55

Phosphorylation of CDC20 at S-41 (S-50 in *X. laevis*) is required for inhibition of the APC/C (Chung & Chen, 2003). Dephosphorylation of CDC20 by PP2A-B55 may be crucial for APC/C activation after spindle assembly checkpoint silencing (Cundell et al., 2016).

7.12. Dephosphorylation of CDCA5 on T-159 by PP2A-B55

CDCA5 (Sororin) is phosphorylated on T-159 by AURKB and CDK1 in vitro and this phosphorylation promotes its release from chromatin in mitosis (Dreier, Bekier & Taylor, 2011; Nishiyama et al., 2013). This site is dephosphorylated by PP2A-B55 (Cundell et al., 2016). PP2A also dephosphorylates Sororin, which helps protect centromeric cohesin from cleavage until the metaphase-anaphase transition (Liu, Rankin & Yu, 2013; Hara et al., 2014).

8. Mid-Spindle Formation during Anaphase-Telophase**8.1. Dephosphorylation of PRC1 on T-470 by PP2A-B55**

Dephosphorylation of T-470 by PP2A-B55 is required for subsequent phosphorylation of the non-motor protein PRC1 by PLK1. This dephosphorylation enhances the microtubule bundling activity of PRC1 at the central-spindle (Cundell et al., 2013; 2016).

8.2. Dephosphorylation of TPX2 on T-369 by PP2A-B55

TPX2 is phosphorylated at T-369 by AURKA. Rapid dephosphorylation of this site by PP2A-B55 is required for the timely relocalisation of TPX2 to the central-spindle during anaphase (Cundell et al., 2016).

8.3. Phosphorylation of PRC1 on S-601 by PLK1

PRC1 is phosphorylated on S-601 and T-602 by PLK1 (Neef et al., 2007; Hu et al., 2012). Phosphorylation of T-481 during mitosis promotes the dephosphorylation of T-602 by PP2A. Dephosphorylation of T-481 during early anaphase, releases this inhibition, allowing PLK1 to phosphorylate S-601/T-602 promoting central-spindle localisation and bundling of microtubules (Cundell et al., 2013; 2016).

8.4. Phosphorylation of RacGAP1 on S-157 by PLK1

PLK1 phosphorylation of RacGAP1 (MgcRacGAP) at S-157 is required for the recruitment of ECT2 to the central-spindle where it promotes RhoA activity and cleavage furrow formation (Burkard et al., 2009; Wolfe et al., 2009). Efficient ECT2 binding also requires phosphorylation of the nearby S-164 site by PLK1 (Kim et al., 2014a). Correct furrow formation requires ECT2 localisation to the plasma membrane (Kotýnková et al., 2016) and is also dependent on the phosphorylation of Anillin at S-635 by an unknown kinase (Kim et al., 2017)

8.5. Dephosphorylation of ARHGEF2 on S-959 by PP2A-B55

Dephosphorylation of S-959 increases the guanine nucleotide exchange activity of ARHGEF2 (GEF-H1). This increased activity

allows GTP loading of RhoA, which is required for cleavage furrow formation (Birkenfeld et al., 2007). S-959 is a proline directed site with a lysine (basic) residue at the +5 position, implicating PP2A-B55 as the potential phosphatase. In support, S-163 on GEF-H1 is dephosphorylated by PP2A-B55 (Cundell et al., 2016).

9. Nuclear Envelope Reformation

9.1. Dephosphorylation of NUP107 on T-46 by PP2A-B55

NUP107 is rapidly dephosphorylated during mitotic exit on multiple sites (McCloy et al., 2015) with T-46 dephosphorylated in a PP2A-B55 dependent manner (Cundell et al., 2016). Dephosphorylation of NUP107 promotes binding with ELYS/Mel28, which recruits Lamin-B receptor (LBR) during nuclear envelope reformation during telophase (Clever et al., 2012).

9.2. Dephosphorylation of POM121C on S-246 by PP2A-B55

POM121C is dephosphorylated on multiple sites during mitotic exit, but to a lesser extent than NUP107 (McCloy et al., 2015) with S-246 on POM121C dephosphorylated in a PP2A-B55 dependent manner (Cundell et al., 2016). POM121C is recruited to the re-forming nuclear pore complex after NUP107 (Bodoor et al., 1999; Antonin et al., 2005).

9.3. Dephosphorylation of NUP153 on S-257 by PP2A-B55

NUP153 is required for timely progression through late mitosis (Mackay, Elgort & Ullman, 2009). Failure to recruit NUP153 to chromosomes activates an AURKB-mediated abscission checkpoint (Mackay, Makise & Ullman, 2010). Multiple phosphorylation sites on NUP153 must be removed for correct recruitment, with S-257 site removed by PP2A-B55 (Cundell et al., 2016). However, Repo-Man (a PP1 subunit) is responsible for recruiting NUP153 to chromosomes during late anaphase/telophase in a PP1-independent manner (Vagnarelli et al., 2011).

9.4. Dephosphorylation of NUP98 on T-553 by PP2A-B55

NUP98 is hyper-phosphorylated by multiple kinases including CDK1 and the NEK family of kinases during mitotic entry (Laurell et al., 2011) with removal of these phosphorylation necessary for efficient reassembly of the nuclear pore during mitotic exit. NUP98 is recruited concomitantly with NUP93 to chromatin during mitotic exit (Dultz et al., 2008) with the T-553 site dephosphorylated in a PP2A-B55 dependent manner (Cundell et al., 2016). NUP98 also plays an important role in preventing APC/C(Cdh1)-mediated ubiquitination of securin prior to anaphase (Jeganathan, Malureanu & van Deursen, 2005). NUP98 fusion oncoproteins, which are found in a variety of cancers including AML (Struski et al., 2017), cause premature mitotic exit and aneuploidy (Salsi et al., 2014) by binding to APC/CDC20 and disrupting its function. Phosphorylation of NUP98 on S-606 regulates its binding to APC/CDC20 (Salsi, Fantini & Zappavigna, 2016).

9.5. Dephosphorylation of LMNB1 on multi-sites by PP1

AKAP149 recruits PP1 at the nuclear envelope (NE) upon nuclear reformation in vitro, and PP1 targeting to the NE is a prerequisite for assembly of B-type lamins (Thompson, Bollen & Fields, 1997; Steen et al., 2000). LMNB1 is concentrated around chromosomes during telophase and is recruited after Lamin-B receptor (LBR), NUPs and POM121C (Moir et al., 2000; Clever et al., 2012). The exact phosphosites targeted by PP1 are unknown but LMNB1 is highly phosphorylated during mitosis, with T-20 and S-28 significantly dephosphorylated during mitotic exit (McCloy et al., 2015).

10. Telophase - Chromatin Decondensation and Cleavage Furrow Formation

10.1. Phosphorylation of AURKB on S-331 by CLK1,2,4

CLK1, CLK2 and CLK4 localize to the midbody in an interdependent manner, associate with and phosphorylate AURKB on S-331, this action completes AURKB activation in telophase (Petsalaki & Zachos, 2016). AURKB activity mediates the abscission checkpoint during cytokinesis to monitor for unsegregated chromatin at the cleavage site and prevent tetraploidization caused by furrow regression (Steigemann et al., 2009). AURKB and ULK3 phosphorylate members of the ESCRT-III complex preventing abscission (Carlton et al., 2012; Thoresen et al., 2014; Caballe et al., 2015).

10.2. Phosphorylation of INCENP on S-894 by LATS1/2

INCENP and AURKB operate in a positive feedback loop through the Thr-Ser-Ser (TSS) motif on INCENP. Phosphorylation of S-894 within the TSS motif by LATS1/2 initiates the positive feedback with AURKB, essential for the completion of cytokinesis (Yabuta et al., 2016).

10.3. Dephosphorylation of HIST1H3A on S-10 by PP1

PP1 is responsible for the dephosphorylation of S-10 on HIST1H3A (Histone H3) during mitotic exit (Hsu et al., 2000; Murnion et al., 2001), which re-establishes the binding of HP1 to chromatin and HIST13AH3 K-9 methylation. The binding of HP1 proteins is critical for the formation of heterochromatin regions, which regulate chromosome organisation and gene expression during the subsequent interphase (Fischle et al., 2005). In addition, PP1-RepoMan also dephosphorylates S-28 on HIST1H3A promoting possible methylation of H3K27, which combined with HP1 binding contributes to the re-establishment of heterochromatin regions. The binding of PP1-RepoMan to NUP153 helps restrict heterochromatin to the nuclear periphery (de Castro et al., 2017).

10.4. Phosphorylation of RacGAP1 on S-387 by AURKB

During late telophase AURKB phosphorylates RacGAP1 (MgcRacGAP) on S-387 at the midbody switching on GAP activity. Active RacGAP1 binds to, and inactivates RhoA at the contractile ring to complete cytokinesis (Minoshima et al., 2003).

10.5. Dephosphorylation of RacGAP1 on S-157 by PP2A-B56

The LxxIxE motif of RacGAP1 (MgcRacGAP) mediates recruitment of PP2A-B56 to the central-spindle, where it dephosphorylates RacGAP1 at S-157 and ensures efficient cytokinesis. This phosphatase recruitment may oppose PLK1 at the midbody, helping to maintain tight control over RacGAP1 activity (Touré et al., 2008; Kim et al., 2014a; Hertz et al., 2016).

References

- Abe S, Nagasaka K, Hirayama Y, Kozuka-Hata H, Oyama M, Aoyagi Y, Obuse C, Hirota T 2011. The initial phase of chromosome condensation requires Cdk1-mediated phosphorylation of the CAP-D3 subunit of condensin II. *Genes & Development* 25:863–874. DOI: 10.1101/gad.2016411.
- Afonso O, Matos I, Pereira AJ, Aguiar P, Lampson MA, Maiato H 2014. Feedback control of chromosome separation by a midzone Aurora B gradient. *Science* 345:332–336. DOI: 10.1126/science.1251121.
- Agircan FG, Schiebel E 2014. Sensors at Centrosomes Reveal Determinants of Local Separase Activity. *PLOS Genetics* 10:e1004672. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1004672.
- Alexandru G, Uhlmann F, Mechtler K, Poupart M-A, Nasmyth K 2001. Phosphorylation of the Cohesin Subunit Scc1 by Polo/Cdc5 Kinase Regulates Sister Chromatid Separation in Yeast. *Cell* 105:459–472. DOI: 10.1016/S0092-8674(01)00362-2.
- Andrews PD, Ovechkina Y, Morrice N, Wagenbach M, Duncan K, Wordeman L, Swedlow JR 2004. Aurora B Regulates MCAK at the

- Mitotic Centromere. *Developmental Cell* 6:253–268. DOI: 10.1016/S1534-5807(04)00025-5.
- Antonin W, Franz C, Haselmann U, Antony C, Mattaj IW 2005. The Integral Membrane Nucleoporin pom121 Functionally Links Nuclear Pore Complex Assembly and Nuclear Envelope Formation. *Molecular Cell* 17:83–92. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2004.12.010.
- Asghar A, Lajeunesse A, Dulla K, Combes G, Thebault P, Nigg EA, Elowe S 2015. Bub1 autophosphorylation feeds back to regulate kinetochore docking and promote localized substrate phosphorylation. *Nature Communications* 6:8364. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms9364.
- Álvarez-Fernández M, Malumbres M 2014. Preparing a cell for nuclear envelope breakdown: Spatio-temporal control of phosphorylation during mitotic entry. *BioEssays* 36:757–765. DOI: 10.1002/bies.201400040.
- Álvarez-Fernández M, Sánchez-Martínez R, Sanz-Castillo B, Gan PP, Sanz-Flores M, Trakala M, Ruiz-Torres M, Lorca T, Castro A, Malumbres M 2013. Greatwall is essential to prevent mitotic collapse after nuclear envelope breakdown in mammals. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110:17374–17379. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1310745110.
- Bagheri-Yarmand R, Nanos-Webb A, Biernacka A, Bui T, Keyomarsi K 2010. Cyclin E deregulation impairs mitotic progression through premature activation of Cdc25C. *Cancer Research* 70:5085–5095. DOI: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-09-4095.
- Ban R, Irino Y, Fukami K, Tanaka H 2004. Human mitotic spindle-associated protein PRC1 inhibits MgcRacGAP activity toward Cdc42 during the metaphase. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 279:16394–16402. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M313257200.
- Ban R, Matsuzaki H, Akashi T, Sakashita G, Taniguchi H, Park S-Y, Tanaka H, Furukawa K, Urano T 2009. Mitotic regulation of the stability of microtubule plus-end tracking protein EB3 by ubiquitin ligase SlAH-1 and Aurora mitotic kinases. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 284:28367–28381. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M109.000273.
- Bayliss R, Sardon T, Vernos I, Conti E 2003. Structural Basis of Aurora-A Activation by TPX2 at the Mitotic Spindle. *Molecular Cell* 12:851–862. DOI: 10.1016/S1097-2765(03)00392-7.
- Bekier ME, Mazur T, Rashid MS, Taylor WR 2015. Borealin dimerization mediates optimal CPC checkpoint function by enhancing localization to centromeres and kinetochores. *Nature Communications* 6:6775. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms7775.
- Bertolin G, Szaire F, Herbomel G, Rebutier D, Prigent C, Tramier M 2016. A FRET biosensor reveals spatiotemporal activation and functions of aurora kinase A in living cells. *Nature Communications* 7:12674. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms12674.
- Bertran MT, Sdelci S, Regué L, Avruch J, Caelles C, Roig J 2011. Nek9 is a Plk1-activated kinase that controls early centrosome separation through Nek6/7 and Eg5. *EMBO Journal* 30:2634–2647. DOI: 10.1038/emboj.2011.179.
- Birkenfeld J, Nalbant P, Bohl BP, Pertz O, Hahn KM, Bokoch GM 2007. GEF-H1 Modulates Localized RhoA Activation during Cytokinesis under the Control of Mitotic Kinases. *Developmental Cell* 12:699–712. DOI: 10.1016/j.devcel.2007.03.014.
- Blake-Hodek KA, Williams BC, Zhao Y, Castilho PV, Chen W, Mao Y, Yamamoto TM, Goldberg ML 2012. Determinants for activation of the atypical AGC kinase Greatwall during M phase entry. *Molecular and Cellular Biology* 32:1337–1353. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.06525-11.
- Blangy A, Lane HA, d'Hérin P, Harper M, Kress M, Nigg EA 1995. Phosphorylation by p34cdc2 regulates spindle association of human Eg5, a kinesin-related motor essential for bipolar spindle formation in vivo. *Cell* 83:1159–1169. DOI: 10.1016/0092-8674(95)90142-6.
- Bodoor K, Shaikh S, Salina D, Raharjo WH, Bastos R, Lohka M, Burke B 1999. Sequential recruitment of NPC proteins to the nuclear periphery at the end of mitosis. *Journal of Cell Science* 112:2253.
- Bourhis E, Lingel A, Phung Q, Fairbrother WJ, Cochran AG 2009. Phosphorylation of a Borealin Dimerization Domain Is Required for Proper Chromosome Segregation. *Biochemistry* 48:6783–6793. DOI: 10.1021/bi900530v.
- Bruinsma W, Aprelia M, García-Santisteban I, Kool J, Xu YJ, Medema RH 2017. Inhibition of Polo-like kinase 1 during the DNA damage response is mediated through loss of Aurora A recruitment by Bora. *Oncogene* 36:1840–1848. DOI: 10.1038/ncr.2016.347.
- Bruinsma W, Macúrek L, Freire R, Lindqvist A, Medema RH 2014. Bora and Aurora-A continue to activate Plk1 in mitosis. *Journal of Cell Science* 127:801–811. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.137216.
- Bulavin DV, Higashimoto Y, Demidenko ZN, Meek S, Graves P, Phillips C, Zhao H, Moody SA, Appella E, Piwnicka-Worms H, Fornace AJ Jr 2003. Dual phosphorylation controls Cdc25 phosphatases and mitotic entry. *Nature Cell Biology* 5:545–551. DOI: 10.1038/ncb994.
- Burgess A, Vuong J, Rogers S, Malumbres M, O'Donoghue SI. SnapShot: Phosphoregulation of Mitosis. *Cell* (2017) 169:1358–1358.e1. doi:10.1016/j.cell.2017.06.003
- Burgess SG, Peset I, Joseph N, Cavazza T, Vernos I, Pfuhl M, Gergely F, Bayliss R 2015. Aurora-A-Dependent Control of TACC3 Influences the Rate of Mitotic Spindle Assembly. *PLOS Genetics* 11:e1005345. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1005345.
- Burkard ME, Maciejowski J, Rodriguez-Bravo V, Repka M, Lowery DM, Clauser KR, Zhang C, Shokat KM, Carr SA, Yaffe MB, Jallepalli PV 2009. Plk1 Self-Organization and Priming Phosphorylation of HsCYK-4 at the Spindle Midzone Regulate the Onset of Division in Human Cells. *PLOS Biology* 7:e1000111. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.1000111.
- Caballe A, Wenzel DM, Agromayor M, Alam SL, Skalicky JJ, Kloc M, Carlton JG, Labrador L, Sundquist WI, Martin-Serrano J 2015. ULK3 regulates cytokinetic abscission by phosphorylating ESCRT-III proteins. *eLife* 4:352. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.06547.
- Carlton JG, Caballe A, Agromayor M, Kloc M, Martin-Serrano J 2012. ESCRT-III governs the Aurora B-mediated abscission checkpoint through CHMP4C. *Science* 336:220–225. DOI: 10.1126/science.1217180.
- Carmena M, Wheelock M, Funabiki H, Earnshaw WC 2012. The chromosomal passenger complex (CPC): from easy rider to the godfather of mitosis. *Nature reviews. Molecular Cell Biology* 13:789–803. DOI: 10.1038/nrm3474.
- Cazales M, Schmitt E, Montebault E, Dozier C, Prigent C, Ducommun B 2005. CDC25B Phosphorylation by Aurora A Occurs at the G2/M Transition and is Inhibited by DNA Damage. *Cell Cycle* 4:1233–1238. DOI: 10.4161/cc.4.9.1964.
- Chou E-J, Hung L-Y, Tang C-JC, Hsu W-B, Wu H-Y, Liao P-C, Tang TK 2016. Phosphorylation of CPAP by Aurora-A Maintains Spindle Pole Integrity during Mitosis. *Cell Reports* 14:2975–2987. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2016.02.085.
- Chung E, Chen R-H 2003. Phosphorylation of Cdc20 is required for its inhibition by the spindle checkpoint. *Nature Cell Biology* 5:748–753. DOI: 10.1038/ncb1022.
- Clever M, Funakoshi T, Mimura Y, Takagi M, Imamoto N 2012. The nucleoporin ELYS/Mel28 regulates nuclear envelope subdomain formation in HeLa cells. *Nucleus* 3:187–199. DOI: 10.4161/nucl.19595.
- Cooke CA, Heck MM, Earnshaw WC 1987. The inner centromere protein (INCENP) antigens: movement from inner centromere to midbody during mitosis. *Journal of Cell Biology* 105:2053–2067. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.105.5.2053.
- Craney A, Kelly A, Jia L, Fedrigo I, Yu H, Rape M 2016. Control of APC/C-dependent ubiquitin chain elongation by reversible phosphorylation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 113:1540–1545. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1522423113.
- Cundell MJ, Bastos RN, Zhang T, Holder J, Gruneberg U, Novak B, Barr FA 2013. The BEG (PP2A-B55/ENSA/Greatwall) pathway ensures cytokinesis follows chromosome separation. *Molecular Cell* 52:393–405. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2013.09.005.
- Cundell MJ, Hutter LH, Nunes Bastos R, Poser E, Holder J, Mohammed S, Novak B, Barr FA 2016. A PP2A-B55 recognition signal controls substrate dephosphorylation kinetics during mitotic exit. *Journal of Cell Biology* 214:539–554. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201606033.
- Dai J, Sultan S, Taylor SS, Higgins JMG 2005. The kinase haspin is required for mitotic histone H3 Thr 3 phosphorylation and normal metaphase chromosome alignment. *Genes & Development* 19:472–488. DOI: 10.1101/gad.1267105.
- De Boer L, Oakes V, Beamish H, Giles N, Stevens F, Somodevilla-Torres M, DeSouza C, Gabrielli B 2008. Cyclin A/cdk2 coordinates

- centrosomal and nuclear mitotic events. *Oncogene* 27:4261–4268. DOI: 10.1038/onc.2008.74.
- de Castro IJ, Budzak J, Di Giacinto ML, Ligammari L, Gokhan E, Spanos C, Moralli D, Richardson C, las Heras de JI, Salatino S, Schirmer EC, Ullman KS, Bickmore WA, Green C, Rappsilber J, Lamble S, Goldberg MW, Vinciotti V, Vagnarelli P 2017. Repo-Man/PP1 regulates heterochromatin formation in interphase. *Nature Communications* 8:14048. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms14048.
- De Souza, Colin P.C., Ellem KAO, Gabrielli BG 2000. Centrosomal and Cytoplasmic Cdc2/Cyclin B1 Activation Precedes Nuclear Mitotic Events. *Experimental Cell Research* 257:11–21. DOI: 10.1006/excr.2000.4872.
- De Souza, Colin P.C., Osmani AH, Hashmi SB, Osmani SA 2004. Partial Nuclear Pore Complex Disassembly during Closed Mitosis in *Aspergillus nidulans*. *Current Biology* 14:1973–1984. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2004.10.050.
- DellaMonica R, Visconti R, Cervone N, Serpico AF, Grieco D 2015. Fcp1 phosphatase controls Greatwall kinase to promote PP2A-B55 activation and mitotic progression. *eLife* 4:1337. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.10399.
- Di Fiore B, Wurzenberger C, Davey NE, Pines J 2016. The Mitotic Checkpoint Complex Requires an Evolutionary Conserved Cassette to Bind and Inhibit Active APC/C. *Molecular Cell* 64:1144–1153. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2016.11.006.
- Diril MK, Bisteau X, Kitagawa M, Caldez MJ, Wee S, Gunaratne J, Lee SH, Kaldis P 2016. Loss of the Greatwall Kinase Weakens the Spindle Assembly Checkpoint. *PLoS Genetics* 12:e1006310. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1006310.
- Dodson CA, Bayliss R 2012. Activation of Aurora-A kinase by protein partner binding and phosphorylation are independent and synergistic. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 287:1150–1157. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M111.312090.
- Dreier MR, Bekier ME 2nd, Taylor WR 2011. Regulation of sororin by Cdk1-mediated phosphorylation. *Journal of cell science* 124:2976–2987. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.085431.
- Duan H, Wang C, Wang M, Gao X, Yan M, Akram S, Peng W, Zou H, Wang D, Zhou J, Chu Y, Dou Z, Barrett G, Green H-N, Wang F, Tian R, He P, Wang W, Liu X, Yao X 2016. Phosphorylation of PP1 Regulator Sds22 by PLK1 Ensures Accurate Chromosome Segregation. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 291:21123–21136. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M116.745372.
- Dultz E, Zanin E, Wurzenberger C, Braun M, Rabut G, Sironi L, Ellenberg J 2008. Systematic kinetic analysis of mitotic dis- and reassembly of the nuclear pore in living cells. *Journal of Cell Biology* 180:857–865. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.200707026.
- Dutertre S, Cazales M, Quaranta M, Froment C, Trabut V, Dozier C, Mirey G, Bouché J-P, Theis-Febvre N, Schmitt E, Monsarrat B, Prigent C, Ducommun B 2004. Phosphorylation of CDC25B by Aurora-A at the centrosome contributes to the G2-M transition. *Journal of cell science* 117:2523–2531. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.01108.
- Elowe S, Dulla K, Uldschmid A, Li X, Dou Z, Nigg EA 2009. Uncoupling of the spindle-checkpoint and chromosome-congression functions of BubR1. *Journal of cell science* 123:84–94. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.056507.
- Elowe S, Hümmel S, Uldschmid A, Li X, Nigg EA 2007. Tension-sensitive Plk1 phosphorylation on BubR1 regulates the stability of kinetochore microtubule interactions. *Genes & Development* 21:2205–2219. DOI: 10.1101/gad.436007.
- Ertych N, Stolz A, Valerius O, Braus GH, Bastians H 2016. CHK2-BRCA1 tumor-suppressor axis restrains oncogenic Aurora-A kinase to ensure proper mitotic microtubule assembly. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 113:1817–1822. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1525129113.
- Fachinetti D, Logsdon GA, Abdullah A, Selzer EB, Cleveland DW, Black BE 2017. CENP-A Modifications on Ser68 and Lys124 Are Dispensable for Establishment, Maintenance, and Long-Term Function of Human Centromeres. *Developmental Cell* 40:104–113.
- Favreau C, Worman HJ, Wozniak RW, Frappier T, Courvalin J-C 1996. Cell Cycle-Dependent Phosphorylation of Nucleoporins and Nuclear Pore Membrane Protein Gp210 †. *Biochemistry* 35:8035–8044. DOI: 10.1021/bi9600660.
- Ferreira JG, Pereira AJ, Akhmanova A, Maiato H 2013. Aurora B spatially regulates EB3 phosphorylation to coordinate daughter cell adhesion with cytokinesis. *Journal of Cell Biology* 201:709–724. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201301131.
- Fischle W, Tseng BS, Dormann HL, Ueberheide BM, Garcia BA, Shabanowitz J, Hunt DF, Funabiki H, Allis CD 2005. Regulation of HP1–chromatin binding by histone H3 methylation and phosphorylation. *Nature* 438:1116–1122. DOI: 10.1038/nature04219.
- Fortugno P, Wall NR, Giodini A, O'Connor DS, Plescia J, Padgett KM, Tognin S, Marchisio PC, Altieri DC 2002. Survivin exists in immunochemically distinct subcellular pools and is involved in spindle microtubule function. *Journal of cell science* 115:575–585. DOI: 10.1038/nm0897-917.
- Fu J, Bian M, Xin G, Deng Z, Luo J, Guo X, Chen H, Wang Y, Jiang Q, Zhang C 2015. TPX2 phosphorylation maintains metaphase spindle length by regulating microtubule flux. *Journal of Cell Biology* 210:373–383. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201412109.
- Fujimitsu K, Grimaldi M, Yamano H 2016. Cyclin-dependent kinase 1-dependent activation of APC/C ubiquitin ligase. *Science* 352:1121–1124. DOI: 10.1126/science.aad3925.
- Gallini S, Carminati M, De Mattia F, Pirovano L, Martini E, Oldani A, Asteriti IA, Guarguaglini G, Mapelli M 2016. NuMA Phosphorylation by Aurora-A Orchestrates Spindle Orientation. *Current Biology* 26:458–469. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2015.12.051.
- Gharbi-Ayachi A, Labbé JC, Burgess A, Vigneron S, Strub J-M, Brioude E, Van-Dorselaer A, Castro A, Lorca T 2010. The substrate of Greatwall kinase, Arpp19, controls mitosis by inhibiting protein phosphatase 2A. *Science* 330:1673–1677. DOI: 10.1126/science.1197048.
- Ghenoiu C, Wheelock MS, Funabiki H 2013. Autoinhibition and Polo-Dependent Multisite Phosphorylation Restrict Activity of the Histone H3 Kinase Haspin to Mitosis. *Molecular Cell* 52:734–745.
- Gomez-Ferreria MA, Bashkurov M, Helbig AO, Larsen B, Pawson T, Gingras A-C, Pelletier L 2012. Novel NEDD1 phosphorylation sites regulate γ -tubulin binding and mitotic spindle assembly. *Journal of cell science* 125:3745–3751. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.105130.
- Gorr IH, Boos D, Stemmann O 2005. Mutual Inhibition of Separase and Cdk1 by Two-Step Complex Formation. *Molecular Cell* 19:135–141. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2005.05.022.
- Goto H, Kiyono T, Tomono Y, Kawajiri A, Urano T, Furukawa K, Nigg EA, Inagaki M 2006. Complex formation of Plk1 and INCENP required for metaphase–anaphase transition. *Nature Cell Biology* 8:180–187. DOI: 10.1038/ncb1350.
- Grallert A, Boke E, Hagting A, Hodgson B, Connolly Y, Griffiths JR, Smith DL, Pines J, Hagan IM 2015. A PP1-PP2A phosphatase relay controls mitotic progression. *Nature* 517:94–98. DOI: 10.1038/nature14019.
- Haq T, Richards MW, Burgess SG, Gallego P, Yeoh S, O'Regan L, Reverter D, Roig J, Fry AM, Bayliss R 2015. Mechanistic basis of Nek7 activation through Nek9 binding and induced dimerization. *Nature Communications* 6:8771. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms9771.
- Hara K, Zheng G, Qu Q, Liu H, Ouyang Z, Chen Z, Tomchick DR, Yu H 2014. Structure of cohesin subcomplex pinpoints direct shugoshin-Wapl antagonism in centromeric cohesion. *Nature Structural & Molecular Biology* 21:864–870. DOI: 10.1038/nsmb.2880.
- Hara T, Abe M, Inoue H, Yu L-R, Veenstra TD, Kang YH, Lee KS, Miki T 2006. Cytokinesis regulator ECT2 changes its conformation through phosphorylation at Thr-341 in G2/M phase. *Oncogene* 25:566–578. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1209078.
- Hardy T, Lee M, Hames RS, Prosser SL, Cheary D-M, Samant MD, Schultz F, Baxter JE, Rhee K, Fry AM 2014. Multisite phosphorylation of C-Nap1 releases it from Cep135 to trigger centrosome disjunction. *Journal of cell science* 127:2493–2506. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.142331.
- Harley ME, Allan LA, Sanderson HS, Clarke PR 2010. Phosphorylation of Mcl-1 by CDK1-cyclin B1 initiates its Cdc20-dependent destruction during mitotic arrest. *The EMBO Journal* 29:2407–2420. DOI: 10.1038/emboj.2010.112.
- Hauf S, Roitinger E, Koch B, Dittrich CM, Mechtler K, Peters J-M 2005. Dissociation of Cohesin from Chromosome Arms and Loss of Arm Cohesion during Early Mitosis Depends on Phosphorylation of SA2. *PLoS Biology* 3:e69. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.0030069.
- Häfner J, Mayr MI, Möckel MM, Mayer TU 2014. Pre-anaphase chromosome oscillations are regulated by the antagonistic activities of Cdk1 and PP1 on Kif18A. *Nature Communications* 5:4397. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms5397.

- He J, Zhang Z, Ouyang M, Yang F, Hao H, Lamb KL, Yang J, Yin Y, Shen WH 2016. PTEN regulates EG5 to control spindle architecture and chromosome congression during mitosis. *Nature Communications* 7:12355. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms12355.
- Heim A, Konietzny A, Mayer TU 2015. Protein phosphatase 1 is essential for Greatwall inactivation at mitotic exit. *EMBO reports* 16:1501–1510. DOI: 10.15252/embr.201540876.
- Hein JB, Nilsson J 2016. Interphase APC/C–Cdc20 inhibition by cyclin A2–Cdk2 ensures efficient mitotic entry. *Nature Communications* 7:10975. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms10975.
- Hellmuth S, Rata S, Brown A, Heidmann S, Novak B, Stemmann O 2015. Human Chromosome Segregation Involves Multi-Layered Regulation of Separase by the Peptidyl-Prolyl-Isomerase Pin1. *Molecular Cell* 58:495–506. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2015.03.025.
- Hertz EPT, Kruse T, Davey NE, López-Méndez B, Sigurðsson JO, Montoya G, Olsen JV, Nilsson J 2016. A Conserved Motif Provides Binding Specificity to the PP2A-B56 Phosphatase. *Molecular Cell* 63:686–695. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2016.06.024.
- Hégarat N, Vesely C, Vinod PK, Ocasio C, Peter N, Gannon J, Oliver AW, Novak B, Hochegger H 2014. PP2A/B55 and Fcp1 regulate Greatwall and Ensa dephosphorylation during mitotic exit. *PLOS Genetics* 10:e1004004. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1004004.
- Hinchcliffe EH, Day CA, Karanjeet KB, Fadness S, Langfald A, Vaughan KT, Dong Z 2016. Chromosome missegregation during anaphase triggers p53 cell cycle arrest through histone H3.3 Ser31 phosphorylation. *Nature Cell Biology* 18:668–675. DOI: 10.1038/ncb3348.
- Hirota T, Lipp JJ, Toh B-H, Peters J-M 2005. Histone H3 serine 10 phosphorylation by Aurora B causes HP1 dissociation from heterochromatin. *Nature* 438:1176–1180. DOI: 10.1038/nature04254.
- Honda R, Körner R, Nigg EA 2003. Exploring the Functional Interactions between Aurora B, INCENP, and Survivin in Mitosis. *MBoC* 14:3325–3341. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e02-11-0769.
- Hou Y, Allan LA, Clarke PR 2017. Phosphorylation of XIAP by CDK1-cyclin-B1 controls mitotic cell death. *Journal of cell science* 130:502–511. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.192310.
- Hsu J-Y, Sun Z-W, Li X, Reuben M, Tatchell K, Bishop DK, Grushcow JM, Brame CJ, Caldwell JA, Hunt DF, Lin R, Smith MM, Allis CD 2000. Mitotic Phosphorylation of Histone H3 Is Governed by Ipl1/aurora Kinase and Glc7/PP1 Phosphatase in Budding Yeast and Nematodes. *Cell* 102:279–291. DOI: 10.1016/S0092-8674(00)00034-9.
- Hu C-K, Özlü N, Coughlin M, Steen JJ, Mitchison TJ 2012. Plk1 negatively regulates PRC1 to prevent premature midzone formation before cytokinesis. *MBoC* 23:2702–2711. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e12-01-0058.
- Huis in 't Veld PJ, Jeganathan S, Petrovic A, Singh P, John J, Krenn V, Weissmann F, Bange T, Musacchio A 2016. Molecular basis of outer kinetochore assembly on CENP-T. *eLife* 5:576. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.21007.
- Hümmer S, Mayer TU 2009. Cdk1 Negatively Regulates Midzone Localization of the Mitotic Kinesin Mklp2 and the Chromosomal Passenger Complex. *Current Biology* 19:607–612. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2009.02.046.
- Imori M, Watanabe S, Kiyonari S, Matsuoka K, Sakasai R, Saeki H, Oki E, Kitao H, Maehara Y 2016. Phosphorylation of EB2 by Aurora B and CDK1 ensures mitotic progression and genome stability. *Nature Communications* 7:11117. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms11117.
- Jackman M, Lindon C, Nigg EA, Pines J 2003. Active cyclin B1–Cdk1 first appears on centrosomes in prophase. *Nature Cell Biology* 5:143–148. DOI: 10.1038/ncb918.
- Jeganathan KB, Malureanu L, van Deursen JM 2005. The Rae1–Nup98 complex prevents aneuploidy by inhibiting securin degradation. *Nature* 438:1036–1039. DOI: 10.1038/nature04221.
- Jelluma N, Brenkman AB, van den Broek NJF, Cruijnsen CWA, van Osch MHJ, Lens SMA, Medema RH, Kops GJPL 2008. Mps1 Phosphorylates Borealin to Control Aurora B Activity and Chromosome Alignment. *Cell* 132:233–246. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2007.11.046.
- Jia L, Li B, Yu H 2016. The Bub1–Plk1 kinase complex promotes spindle checkpoint signalling through Cdc20 phosphorylation. *Nature Communications* 7:10818. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms10818.
- Joukov V, Walter JC, De Nicolo A 2014. The Cep192-Organized Aurora A-Plk1 Cascade Is Essential for Centrosome Cycle and Bipolar Spindle Assembly. *Molecular Cell* 55:578–591. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2014.06.016.
- Kajtez J, Solomatina A, Novak M, Polak B, Vukušić K, Rüdiger J, Cojoc G, Milas A, Šestak IŠ, Risteski P, Tavano F, Klemm AH, Roscioli E, Welburn J, Cimini D, Glunčić M, Pavin N, Tolić IM 2016. Overlap microtubules link sister k-fibres and balance the forces on bi-oriented kinetochores. *Nature Communications* 7:10298. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms10298.
- Kalantzaki M, Kitamura E, Zhang T, Mino A, Novak B, Tanaka TU 2015. Kinetochore–microtubule error correction is driven by differentially regulated interaction modes. *Nature Cell Biology* 17:421–433. DOI: 10.1038/ncb3128.
- Kaneta Y, Ullrich A 2013. NEK9 depletion induces catastrophic mitosis by impairment of mitotic checkpoint control and spindle dynamics. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications* 442:139–146. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbrc.2013.04.105.
- Karlsson C, Katich S, Hagting A, Hoffmann I, Pines J 1999. Cdc25B and Cdc25C differ markedly in their properties as initiators of mitosis. *Journal of Cell Biology* 146:573–584. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.146.3.573.
- Kawashima SA, Yamagishi Y, Honda T, Ishiguro K-I, Watanabe Y 2010. Phosphorylation of H2A by Bub1 prevents chromosomal instability through localizing shugoshin. *Science* 327:172–177. DOI: 10.1126/science.1180189.
- Kelly AE, Ghenoiu C, Xue JZ, Zierhut C, Kimura H, Funabiki H 2010. Survivin reads phosphorylated histone H3 threonine 3 to activate the mitotic kinase Aurora B. *Science* 330:235–239. DOI: 10.1126/science.1189505.
- Kim H, Guo F, Brahma S, Xing Y, Burkard ME 2014a. Centralspindlin assembly and 2 phosphorylations on MgcRacGAP by Polo-like kinase 1 initiate Ect2 binding in early cytokinesis. *Cell Cycle* 13:2952–2961. DOI: 10.4161/15384101.2014.947201.
- Kim H, Johnson JM, Lera RF, Brahma S, Burkard ME 2017. Anillin Phosphorylation Controls Timely Membrane Association and Successful Cytokinesis. *PLOS Genetics* 13:e1006511. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1006511.
- Kim JH, Shim J, Ji M-J, Jung Y, Bong SM, Jang Y-J, Yoon E-K, Lee S-J, Kim KG, Kim YH, Lee C, Lee II B, Kim K-T 2014b. The condensin component NCAPG2 regulates microtubule–kinetochore attachment through recruitment of Polo-like kinase 1 to kinetochores. *Nature Communications* 5:4588. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms5588.
- Kim S, Yu H 2015. Multiple assembly mechanisms anchor the KMN spindle checkpoint platform at human mitotic kinetochores. *Journal of Cell Biology* 208:181–196. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201407074.
- Kim S, Kim S, Rhee K 2011. NEK7 is essential for centriole duplication and centrosomal accumulation of pericentriolar material proteins in interphase cells. *Journal of cell science* 124:3760–3770. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.078089.
- Kitagawa M, Fung SYS, Hameed UFS, Goto H, Inagaki M, Lee SH 2014. Cdk1 Coordinates Timely Activation of Mklp2 Kinesin with Relocation of the Chromosome Passenger Complex for Cytokinesis. *Cell reports* 7:166–179. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2014.02.034.
- Kosako H, Yamaguchi N, Aranami C, Ushiyama M, Kose S, Imamoto N, Taniguchi H, Nishida E, Hattori S 2009. Phosphoproteomics reveals new ERK MAP kinase targets and links ERK to nucleoporin-mediated nuclear transport. *Nature Structural & Molecular Biology* 16:1026–1035. DOI: 10.1038/nsmb.1656.
- Kotýnková K, Su K-C, West SC, Petronczki M 2016. Plasma Membrane Association but Not Midzone Recruitment of RhoGEF ECT2 Is Essential for Cytokinesis. *Cell reports* 17:2672–2686.
- Kruse T, Zhang G, Larsen MSY, Lischetti T, Streicher W, Kragh Nielsen T, Bjørn SP, Nilsson J 2013. Direct binding between BubR1 and B56-PP2A phosphatase complexes regulate mitotic progression. *Journal of cell science* 126:1086–1092. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.122481.
- Kunitoku N, Sasayama T, Marumoto T, Zhang D, Honda S, Kobayashi O, Hatakeyama K, Ushio Y, Saya H, Hirota T 2003. CENP-A Phosphorylation by Aurora-A in Prophase Is Required for Enrichment of Aurora-B at Inner Centromeres and for Kinetochore Function. *Developmental Cell* 5:853–864. DOI: 10.1016/S1534-5807(03)00364-2.

- Kurioka D, Takeshita F, Tsuta K, Sakamoto H, Watanabe S-I, Matsumoto K, Watanabe M, Nakagama H, Ochiya T, Yokota J, Kohno T, Tsuchiya N 2014. NEK9-dependent proliferation of cancer cells lacking functional p53. *Scientific Reports* 4:6111. DOI: 10.1038/srep06111.
- Laurell E, Beck K, Krupina K, Theerthagiri G, Bodenmiller B, Horvath P, Aebbersold R, Antonin W, Kutay U 2011. Phosphorylation of Nup98 by Multiple Kinases Is Crucial for NPC Disassembly during Mitotic Entry. *Cell* 144:539–550. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2011.01.012.
- Lens SMA, Wolthuis RMF, Klompmaker R, Kauw J, Agami R, Brummelkamp T, Kops G, Medema RH 2003. Survivin is required for a sustained spindle checkpoint arrest in response to lack of tension. *The EMBO Journal* 22:2934–2947. DOI: 10.1093/emboj/cdg307.
- Lera RF, Potts GK, Suzuki A, Johnson JM, Salmon ED, Coon JJ, Burkard ME 2016. Decoding Polo-like kinase 1 signaling along the kinetochore–centromere axis. *Nature Chemical Biology* 12:411–418. DOI: 10.1038/nchembio.2060.
- LeRoy PJ, Hunter JJ, Hoar KM, Burke KE, Shinde V, Ruan J, Bowman D, Galvin K, Ecsedy JA 2007. Localization of human TACC3 to mitotic spindles is mediated by phosphorylation on Ser558 by Aurora A: a novel pharmacodynamic method for measuring Aurora A activity. *Cancer Res* 67:5362–5370. DOI: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-07-0122.
- Lin C-H, Hu C-K, Shih H-M 2010. Clathrin heavy chain mediates TACC3 targeting to mitotic spindles to ensure spindle stability. *Journal of Cell Biology* 189:1097–1105. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.200911120.
- Lin Z, Luo X, Yu H 2016. Structural basis of cohesin cleavage by separase. *Nature* 532:131–134. DOI: 10.1038/nature17402.
- Lindqvist A, Källström H, Lundgren A, Barsoum E, Rosenthal CK 2005. Cdc25B cooperates with Cdc25A to induce mitosis but has a unique role in activating cyclin B1-Cdk1 at the centrosome. *Journal of Cell Biology* 171:35–45. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.200503066.
- Liu H, Jia L, Yu H 2013. Phospho-H2A and Cohesin Specify Distinct Tension-Regulated Sgo1 Pools at Kinetochores and Inner Centromeres. *Current Biology* 23:1927–1933.
- Liu H, Rankin S, Yu H 2013. Phosphorylation-enabled binding of SGO1–PP2A to cohesin protects sororin and centromeric cohesion during mitosis. *Nature Cell Biology* 15:40–49. DOI: 10.1038/ncb2637.
- Lorca T, Bernis C, Vigneron S, Burgess A, Brioudes E, Labbé JC, Castro A 2010. Constant regulation of both the MPF amplification loop and the Greatwall-PP2A pathway is required for metaphase II arrest and correct entry into the first embryonic cell cycle. *Journal of cell science* 123:2281–2291. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.064527.
- Ma DKG, Stolte C, Kaur S, Bain M, O'Donoghue SI 2013. Visual analytics of phosphorylation time-series data on insulin response. in (AIP), 185–196. doi:10.1063/1.4825010
- Ma S, Vigneron S, Robert P, Strub J-M, Cianferani S, Castro A, Lorca T 2016. Greatwall dephosphorylation and inactivation upon mitotic exit is triggered by PP1. *Journal of cell science* 129:1329–1339. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.178855.
- Mackay DR, Elgort SW, Ullman KS 2009. The Nucleoporin Nup153 Has Separable Roles in Both Early Mitotic Progression and the Resolution of Mitosis. *MBoC* 20:1652–1660. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e08-08-0883.
- Mackay DR, Makise M, Ullman KS 2010. Defects in nuclear pore assembly lead to activation of an Aurora B-mediated abscission checkpoint. *Journal of Cell Biology* 191:923–931. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201007124.
- Macûrek L, Lindqvist A, Lim D, Lampson MA, Klompmaker R, Freire R, Clouin C, Taylor SS, Yaffe MB, Medema RH 2008. Polo-like kinase-1 is activated by aurora A to promote checkpoint recovery. *Nature* 455:119–123. DOI: 10.1038/nature07185.
- Maia ARR, Garcia Z, Kabeche L, Barisic M, Maffini S, Macedo-Ribeiro S, Cheeseman IM, Compton DA, Kaverina I, Maiato H 2012. Cdk1 and Plk1 mediate a CLASP2 phospho-switch that stabilizes kinetochore-microtubule attachments. *Journal of Cell Biology* 199:285–301. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201203091.
- Mall M, Walter T, Gorjánác M, Davidson IF, Nga Ly-Hartig TB, Ellenberg J, Mattaj JW 2012. Mitotic lamin disassembly is triggered by lipid-mediated signaling. *Journal of Cell Biology* 198:981–990. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201205103.
- Mardin BR, Agircan FG, Lange C, Schiebel E 2011. Plk1 Controls the Nek2A-PP1 γ Antagonism in Centrosome Disjunction. *Current Biology* 21:1145–1151. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2011.05.047.
- Mazzolini L, Broban A, Froment C, Burlet-Schiltz O, Besson A, Manenti S, Dozier C 2016. Phosphorylation of CDC25A on SER283 in late S/G2 by CDK/cyclin complexes accelerates mitotic entry. *Cell Cycle* 15:2742–2752. DOI: 10.1080/15384101.2016.1220455.
- McCloy RA, Parker BL, Rogers S, Chaudhuri R, Gayevskiy V, Hoffman NJ, Ali N, Watkins DN, Daly RJ, James DE, Lorca T, Castro A, Burgess A 2015. Global Phosphoproteomic Mapping of Early Mitotic Exit in Human Cells Identifies Novel Substrate Dephosphorylation Motifs. *Molecular & cellular proteomics : MCP* 14:2194–2212. DOI: 10.1074/mcp.M114.046938.
- Minoshima Y, Kawashima T, Hirose K, Tonozuka Y, Kawajiri A, Bao YC, Deng X, Tatsuka M, Narumiya S, May WS Jr., Nosaka T, Semba K, Inoue T, Satoh T, Inagaki M, Kitamura T 2003. Phosphorylation by Aurora B Converts MgcRacGAP to a RhoGAP during Cytokinesis. *Developmental Cell* 4:549–560. DOI: 10.1016/S1534-5807(03)00089-3.
- Mitra J, Enders GH 2004. Cyclin A/Cdk2 complexes regulate activation of Cdk1 and Cdc25 phosphatases in human cells. *Oncogene* 23:3361–3367. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1207446.
- Mochida S 2014. Regulation of α -endosulfine, an inhibitor of protein phosphatase 2A, by multisite phosphorylation. *FEBS Journal* 281:1159–1169. DOI: 10.1111/febs.12685.
- Mochida S, Maslen SL, Skehel M, Hunt T 2010. Greatwall phosphorylates an inhibitor of protein phosphatase 2A that is essential for mitosis. *Science* 330:1670–1673. DOI: 10.1126/science.1195689.
- Mochida S, Rata S, Hino H, Nagai T, Novak B 2016. Two Bistable Switches Govern M Phase Entry. *Current biology : CB* 26:3361–3367. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2016.10.022.
- Moir RD, Yoon M, Khuon S, Goldman RD 2000. Nuclear lamins A and B1: different pathways of assembly during nuclear envelope formation in living cells. *Journal of Cell Biology* 151:1155–1168. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.151.6.1155.
- Monier K, Mouradian S, Sullivan KF 2007. DNA methylation promotes Aurora-B-driven phosphorylation of histone H3 in chromosomal subdomains. *Journal of cell science* 120:101–114. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.03326.
- Mori D, Yano Y, Toyo-oka K, Yoshida N, Yamada M, Muramatsu M, Zhang D, Saya H, Toyoshima YY, Kinoshita K, Wynshaw-Boris A, Hirotsune S 2007. NDEL1 phosphorylation by Aurora-A kinase is essential for centrosomal maturation, separation, and TACC3 recruitment. *Molecular and cellular biology* 27:352–367. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00878-06.
- Murnion ME, Adams RR, Callister DM, Allis CD, Earnshaw WC, Swedlow JR 2001. Chromatin-associated protein phosphatase 1 regulates aurora-B and histone H3 phosphorylation. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 276:26656–26665.
- Müller S, Montes de Oca R, Lacoste N, Dingli F, Loew D, Almouzni G 2014. Phosphorylation and DNA Binding of HJURP Determine Its Centromeric Recruitment and Function in CenH3CENP-A Loading. *Cell reports* 8:190–203. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2014.06.002.
- Nam H-J, van Deursen JM 2014. Cyclin B2 and p53 control proper timing of centrosome separation. *Nature Cell Biology* 16:535–546. DOI: 10.1038/ncb2952.
- Neef R, Gruneberg U, Kopajtich R, Li X, Nigg EA, Sillje H, Barr FA 2007. Choice of Plk1 docking partners during mitosis and cytokinesis is controlled by the activation state of Cdk1. *Nature Cell Biology* 9:436–444. DOI: 10.1038/ncb1557.
- Niia F, Tatsumoto T, Lee KS, Miki T 2006. Phosphorylation of the cytokinesis regulator ECT2 at G2/M phase stimulates association of the mitotic kinase Plk1 and accumulation of GTP-bound RhoA. *Oncogene* 25:827–837. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1209124.
- Nijenhuis W, Vallardi G, Teixeira A, Kops GJPL, Saurin AT 2014. Negative feedback at kinetochores underlies a responsive spindle checkpoint signal. *Nature Cell Biology* 16:1257–1264. DOI: 10.1038/ncb3065.
- Nishiyama T, Sykora MM, Huis in 't Veld PJ, Mechtler K, Peters J-M 2013. Aurora B and Cdk1 mediate Wapl activation and release of acetylated cohesin from chromosomes by phosphorylating Sororin. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 110:13404–13409. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1305020110.

- Nozawa R-S, Nagao K, Masuda H-T, Iwasaki O, Hirota T, Nozaki N, Kimura H, Obuse C 2010. Human POGZ modulates dissociation of HP1 α from mitotic chromosome arms through Aurora B activation. *Nature Cell Biology* 12:719–727. DOI: 10.1038/ncb2075.
- O'Connor DS, Grossman D, Plescia J, Li F, Zhang H, Villa A, Tognin S, Marchisio PC, Altieri DC 2000. Regulation of apoptosis at cell division by p34cdc2 phosphorylation of survivin. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 97:13103–13107. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.240390697.
- O'Donoghue SI, Sabir KS, Kalemamov M, Stolte C, Wellmann B, Ho V, Roos M, Perdigão N, Buske FA, Heinrich J, Rost B, Schaffnerhans A 2015. Aquaria: simplifying discovery and insight from protein structures. *Nature Methods*. Feb;12(2):98-9. doi: 10.1038/nmeth.3258.
- Ohashi S, Sakashita G, Ban R, Nagasawa M, Matsuzaki H, Murata Y, Taniguchi H, Shima H, Furukawa K, Urano T 2006. Phosphoregulation of human protein kinase Aurora-A: analysis using anti-phospho-Thr288 monoclonal antibodies. *Oncogene* 25:7691–7702. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1209754.
- Okumura E, Morita A, Wakai M, Mochida S, Hara M, Kishimoto T 2014. Cyclin B-Cdk1 inhibits protein phosphatase PP2A-B55 via a Greatwall kinase-independent mechanism. *Journal of Cell Biology* 204:881–889. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201307160.
- Olsen JV, Vermeulen M, Santamaria A, Kumar C, Miller ML, Jensen LJ, Gnad F, Cox J, Jensen TS, Nigg EA, Brunak S, Mann M 2010. Quantitative phosphoproteomics reveals widespread full phosphorylation site occupancy during mitosis. *Science Signaling*. Jan 12;3(104):ra3. doi: 10.1126/scisignal.2000475.
- Ono T, Fang Y, Spector DL, Hirano T 2004. Spatial and Temporal Regulation of Condensins I and II in Mitotic Chromosome Assembly in Human Cells. *MBoC* 15:3296–3308. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e04-03-0242.
- Pan D, Klare K, Petrovic A, Take A, Walstein K, Singh P, Rondelet A, Bird AW, Musacchio A 2017. CDK-regulated dimerization of M18BP1 on a Mis18 hexamer is necessary for CENP-A loading. *eLife* 6:e02137. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.23352.
- Pemble H, Kumar P, van Haren J, Wittmann T 2017. GSK3-mediated CLASP2 phosphorylation modulates kinetochore dynamics. *Journal of cell science* 130:1404–1412. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.194662.
- Petrone A, Adamo ME, Cheng C, Kettenbach AN 2016. Identification of Candidate Cyclin-dependent kinase 1 (Cdk1) Substrates in Mitosis by Quantitative Phosphoproteomics. *Molecular & cellular proteomics* 15:2448–2461. DOI: 10.1074/mcp.M116.059394.
- Petsalaki E, Zachos G 2016. Clks 1, 2 and 4 prevent chromatin breakage by regulating the Aurora B-dependent abscission checkpoint. *Nature Communications* 7:11451. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms11451.
- Petsalaki E, Akoumianaki T, Black EJ, Gillespie DAF, Zachos G 2011. Phosphorylation at serine 331 is required for Aurora B activation. *Journal of Cell Biology* 195:449–466. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201104023.
- Polak B, Risteski P, Lesjak S, Tolić IM 2017. PRC1-labeled microtubule bundles and kinetochore pairs show one-to-one association in metaphase. *EMBO reports* 18:217–230. DOI: 10.15252/embr.201642650.
- Poon RY, Jiang W, Toyoshima H, Hunter T 1996. Cyclin-dependent kinases are inactivated by a combination of p21 and Thr-14/Tyr-15 phosphorylation after UV-induced DNA damage. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 271:13283–13291. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.271.22.13283.
- Potapova TA, Sivakumar S, Flynn JN, Li R, Gorskys GJ 2011. Mitotic progression becomes irreversible in prometaphase and collapses when Wee1 and Cdc25 are inhibited. *MBoC* 22:1191–1206. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e10-07-0599.
- Qi W, Tang Z, Yu H 2006. Phosphorylation- and Polo-Box-dependent Binding of Plk1 to Bub1 Is Required for the Kinetochore Localization of Plk1. *MBoC* 17:3705–3716. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e06-03-0240.
- Qian J, Beullens M, Huang J, De Munter S, Lesage B, Bollen M 2015. Cdk1 orders mitotic events through coordination of a chromosome-associated phosphatase switch. *Nature Communications* 6:10215. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms10215.
- Qian J, Beullens M, Lesage B, Bollen M 2013. Aurora B Defines Its Own Chromosomal Targeting by Opposing the Recruitment of the Phosphatase Scaffold Repo-Man. *Current Biology* 23:1136–1143. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2013.05.017.
- Qian J, Lesage B, Beullens M, Van Eynde A, Bollen M 2011. PP1/Repo-Man Dephosphorylates Mitotic Histone H3 at T3 and Regulates Chromosomal Aurora B Targeting. *Current Biology* 21:766–773.
- Qiao R, Weissmann F, Yamaguchi M, Brown NG, VanderLinden R, Imre R, Jarvis MA, Brunner MR, Davidson IF, Litos G, Haselbach D, Mechtler K, Stark H, Schulman BA, Peters J-M 2016. Mechanism of APC/CCDC20 activation by mitotic phosphorylation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 113:E2570–8. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1604929113.
- Reboutier D, Troadec M-B, Cremet J-Y, Fukasawa K, Prigent C 2012. Nucleophosmin/B23 activates Aurora A at the centrosome through phosphorylation of serine 89. *Journal of Cell Biology* 197:19–26. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201107134.
- Robertson J, Jacquemet G, Byron A, Jones MC, Warwood S, Selley JN, Knight D, Humphries JD, Humphries MJ 2015. Defining the phospho-adhesome through the phosphoproteomic analysis of integrin signalling. *Nature Communications* 6:6265. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms7265.
- Rogers S, Fey D, McCloy RA, Parker BL, Mitchell NJ, Payne RJ, Daly RJ, James DE, Caldon CE, Watkins DN, Croucher DR, Burgess A 2016. PP1 initiates the dephosphorylation of MASTL, triggering mitotic exit and bistability in human cells. *Journal of cell science* 129:1340–1354. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.179754.
- Salsi V, Fantini S, Zappavigna V 2016. NUP98 fusion oncoproteins interact with the APC/C Cdc20as a pseudosubstrate and prevent mitotic checkpoint complex binding. *Cell Cycle* 15:2275–2287. DOI: 10.1080/15384101.2016.1172156.
- Salsi V, Ferrari S, Gorello P, Fantini S, Chiavolelli F, Mecucci C, Zappavigna V 2014. NUP98 fusion oncoproteins promote aneuploidy by attenuating the mitotic spindle checkpoint. *Cancer Res* 74:1079–1090. DOI: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-13-0912.
- Santos SDM, Wollman R, Meyer T, Ferrell JE Jr. 2012. Spatial Positive Feedback at the Onset of Mitosis. *Cell* 149:1500–1513. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2012.05.028.
- Sardon T, Pache RA, Stein A, Molina H, Vernos I, Aloy P 2010. Uncovering new substrates for Aurora A kinase. *EMBO reports* 11:977–984. DOI: 10.1038/embor.2010.171.
- Satinover DL, Leach CA, Stukenberg PT, Brautigan DL 2004. Activation of Aurora-A kinase by protein phosphatase inhibitor-2, a bifunctional signaling protein. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 101:8625–8630. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0402966101.
- Schubert von C, Cubizolles F, Bracher JM, Sliedrecht T, Kops GJPL, Nigg EA 2015. Plk1 and Mps1 Cooperatively Regulate the Spindle Assembly Checkpoint in Human Cells. *Cell reports* 12:66–78. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2015.06.007.
- Sdelci S, Schütz M, Pinyol R, Bertran MT, Regué L, Caelles C, Vernos I, Roig J 2012. Nek9 Phosphorylation of NEDD1/GCP-WD Contributes to Plk1 Control of γ -Tubulin Recruitment to the Mitotic Centrosome. *Current Biology* 22:1516–1523. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2012.06.027.
- Seki A, Coppinger JA, Jang C-Y, Yates JR, Fang G 2008. Bora and the kinase Aurora cooperatively activate the kinase Plk1 and control mitotic entry. *Science* 320:1655–1658. DOI: 10.1126/science.1157425.
- Sessa F, Mapelli M, Ciferri C, Tarricone C, Arecas LB, Schneider TR, Stukenberg PT, Musacchio A 2005. Mechanism of Aurora B Activation by INCENP and Inhibition by Hesperadin. *Molecular Cell* 18:379–391.
- Shao H, Huang Y, Zhang L, Yuan K, Chu Y, Dou Z, Jin C, Garcia-Barrio M, Liu X, Yao X 2015. Spatiotemporal dynamics of Aurora B-PLK1-MCAK signaling axis orchestrates kinetochore bi-orientation and faithful chromosome segregation. *Scientific Reports* 5:12204. DOI: 10.1038/srep12204.
- Shim SY, Perez de Castro I, Neumayer G, Wang J, Park SK, Sanada K, Nguyen MD 2015. Phosphorylation of targeting protein for Xenopus kinesin-like protein 2 (TPX2) at threonine 72 in spindle assembly. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 290:9122–9134. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M114.591545.
- Shimada M, Goshima T, Matsuo H, Johmura Y, Haruta M, Murata K, Tanaka H, Ikawa M, Nakanishi K, Nakanishi M 2016. Essential role of autoactivation circuitry on Aurora B-mediated H2AX-pS121 in mitosis. *Nature Communications* 7:12059. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms12059.

- Sivakumar S, Janczyk PŁ, Qu Q, Brautigam CA, Stukenberg PT, Yu H, Gorbsky GJ 2016. The human SKA complex drives the metaphase-anaphase cell cycle transition by recruiting protein phosphatase 1 to kinetochores. *eLife* 5:868. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.12902.
- Smith E, Hégarat N, Vesely C, Roseboom I, Larch C, Streicher H, Straatman K, Flynn H, Skehel M, Hirota T, Kuriyama R, Hochegger H 2011. Differential control of Eg5-dependent centrosome separation by Plk1 and Cdk1. *The EMBO Journal* 30:2233–2245. DOI: 10.1038/emboj.2011.120.
- Smoyer CJ, Jaspersen SL 2014. Breaking down the wall: the nuclear envelope during mitosis. *Current opinion in cell biology* 26:1–9.
- Stankovic A, Guo LY, Mata JF, Bodor DL, Cao X-J, Bailey AO, Shabanowitz J, Hunt DF, Garcia BA, Black BE, Jansen LET 2017. A Dual Inhibitory Mechanism Sufficient to Maintain Cell-Cycle-Restricted CENP-A Assembly. *Molecular Cell* 65:231–246.
- Steen RL, Martins SB, Taskén K, Collas P 2000. Recruitment of protein phosphatase 1 to the nuclear envelope by A-kinase anchoring protein AKAP149 is a prerequisite for nuclear lamina assembly. *Journal of Cell Biology* 150:1251–1262. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.150.6.1251.
- Steigemann P, Wurzenberger C, Schmitz MHA, Held M, Guizetti J, Maar S, Gerlich DW 2009. Aurora B-Mediated Abscission Checkpoint Protects against Tetraploidization. *Cell* 136:473–484.
- Struski S, Lagarde S, Bories P, Puisieux C, Prade N, Cucchini W, Pages M-P, Bidet A, Gervais C, Lafage-Pochitaloff M, Roche-Lestienne C, Barin C, Penther D, Nadal N, Radford-Weiss I, Collonge-Rame M-A, Gaillard B, Mugneret F, Lefebvre C, Bart-Delabesse E, Petit A, Leverger G, Broccardo C, Luquet I, Pasquet M, Delabesse E 2017. NUP98 is rearranged in 3.8% of pediatric AML forming a clinical and molecular homogenous group with a poor prognosis. *Leukemia* 31:565–572. DOI: 10.1038/leu.2016.267.
- Sun L, Gao J, Huo L, Sun X, Shi X, Liu M, Li D, Zhang C, Zhou J 2010. Tumour suppressor CYLD is a negative regulator of the mitotic kinase Aurora-B. *The Journal of Pathology* 31:n/a–n/a. DOI: 10.1002/path.2723.
- Tan R, Nakajima S, Wang Q, Sun H, Xue J, Wu J, Hellwig S, Zeng X, Yates NA, Smithgall TE, Lei M, Jiang Y, Levine AS, Su B, Lan L 2017. Nek7 Protects Telomeres from Oxidative DNA Damage by Phosphorylation and Stabilization of TRF1. *Molecular Cell* 65:818–831.e5. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2017.01.015.
- Tang Z, Shu H, Oncel D, Chen S, Yu H 2004a. Phosphorylation of Cdc20 by Bub1 Provides a Catalytic Mechanism for APC/C Inhibition by the Spindle Checkpoint. *Molecular Cell* 16:387–397.
- Tang Z, Sun Y, Harley SE, Zou H, Yu H 2004b. Human Bub1 protects centromeric sister-chromatid cohesion through Shugoshin during mitosis. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 101:18012–18017. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0408600102.
- Thomas Y, Cirillo L, Panbianco C, Martino L, Tavernier N, Schwager F, Van Hove L, Joly N, Santamaria A, Pintard L, Gotta M 2016. Cdk1 Phosphorylates SPAT-1/Bora to Promote Plk1 Activation in *C. elegans* and Human Cells. *Cell reports* 15:510–518. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2016.03.049.
- Thompson LJ, Bollen M, Fields AP 1997. Identification of protein phosphatase 1 as a mitotic lamin phosphatase. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 272:29693–29697.
- Thoresen SB, Campsteijn C, Vietri M, Schink KO, Liestøl K, Andersen JS, Raiborg C, Stenmark H 2014. ANCHR mediates Aurora-B-dependent abscission checkpoint control through retention of VPS4. *Nature Cell Biology* 16:547–557. DOI: 10.1038/ncb2959.
- Touré A, Mzali R, Liot C, Seguin L, Morin L, Crouin C, Chen-Yang I, Tsay Y-G, Dorseuil O, Gacon G, Bertoglio J 2008. Phosphoregulation of MgcRacGAP in mitosis involves Aurora B and Cdk1 protein kinases and the PP2A phosphatase. *FEBS Letters* 582:1182–1188. DOI: 10.1016/j.febslet.2007.12.036.
- Toyoshima-Morimoto F, Taniguchi E, Shinya N, Iwamatsu A, Nishida E 2001. Polo-like kinase 1 phosphorylates cyclin B1 and targets it to the nucleus during prophase. *Nature* 410:215–220. DOI: 10.1038/35065617.
- Trunnell NB, Poon AC, Kim SY, Ferrell JE Jr. 2011. Ultrasensitivity in the Regulation of Cdc25C by Cdk1. *Molecular Cell* 41:263–274. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2011.01.012.
- Tsukahara T, Tanno Y, Watanabe Y 2010. Phosphorylation of the CPC by Cdk1 promotes chromosome bi-orientation. *Nature* 467:719–723. DOI: 10.1038/nature09390.
- UniProt Consortium 2019. UniProt: a worldwide hub of protein knowledge. *Nucleic Acids Res.* Jan 8;47(D1):D506–D515. doi: 10.1093/nar/gky1049.
- Vagnarelli P, Ribeiro S, Sennels L, Sanchez-Pulido L, de Lima Alves F, Verheyen T, Kelly DA, Ponting CP, Rappsilber J, Earnshaw WC 2011. Repo-Man Coordinates Chromosomal Reorganization with Nuclear Envelope Reassembly during Mitotic Exit. *Developmental Cell* 21:328–342. DOI: 10.1016/j.devcel.2011.06.020.
- Vázquez-Novelle MD, Petronczki M 2010. Relocation of the Chromosomal Passenger Complex Prevents Mitotic Checkpoint Engagement at Anaphase. *Current Biology* 20:1402–1407. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2010.06.036.
- Vigneron S, Gharbi-Ayachi A, Raymond A-A, Burgess A, Labbé JC, Labesse G, Monsarrat B, Lorca T, Castro A 2011. Characterization of the mechanisms controlling Greatwall activity. *Molecular and cellular biology* 31:2262–2275. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00753-10.
- Vleugel M, Omerzu M, Groenewold V, Hadders MA, Lens SMA, Kops GJPL 2015. Sequential Multisite Phospho-Regulation of KNL1-BUB3 Interfaces at Mitotic Kinetochores. *Molecular Cell* 57:824–835.
- Walter AO, Seghezzi W, Korver W, Sheung J, Lees E 2000. The mitotic serine/threonine kinase Aurora2/AIK is regulated by phosphorylation and degradation. *Oncogene* 19:4906–4916. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1203847.
- Wang F, Dai J, Daum JR, Niedzialkowska E, Banerjee B, Stukenberg PT, Gorbsky GJ, Higgins JMG 2010. Histone H3 Thr-3 phosphorylation by Haspin positions Aurora B at centromeres in mitosis. *Science* 330:231–235. DOI: 10.1126/science.1189435.
- Wang F, Ulyanova NP, van der Waal MS, Patnaik D, Lens SMA, Higgins JMG 2011. A Positive Feedback Loop Involving Haspin and Aurora B Promotes CPC Accumulation at Centromeres in Mitosis. *Current Biology* 21:1061–1069. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2011.05.016.
- Wang P, Galan JA, Normandin K, Bonneil É, Hickson GR, Roux PP, Thibault P, Archambault V 2013. Cell cycle regulation of Greatwall kinase nuclear localization facilitates mitotic progression. *Journal of Cell Biology* 202:277–293. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201211141.
- Wei J-H, Zhang ZC, Wynn RM, Seemann J 2015. GM130 Regulates Golgi-Derived Spindle Assembly by Activating TPX2 and Capturing Microtubules. *Cell* 162:287–299. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2015.06.014.
- Welburn JPI, Vleugel M, Liu D, Yates JR III, Lampson MA, Fukagawa T, Cheeseman IM 2010. Aurora B Phosphorylates Spatially Distinct Targets to Differentially Regulate the Kinetochore-Microtubule Interface. *Molecular Cell* 38:383–392. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2010.02.034.
- Wheelock MS, Wynne DJ, Tseng BS, Funabiki H 2017. Dual recognition of chromatin and microtubules by INCENP is important for mitotic progression. *Journal of Cell Biology* 216:925–941. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201609061.
- Wike CL, Graves HK, Hawkins R, Gibson MD, Ferdinand MB, Zhang T, Chen Z, Hudson DF, Ottesen JJ, Poirier HG, Schumacher J, Tyler JK 2016. Aurora-A mediated histone H3 phosphorylation of threonine 118 controls condensin I and cohesin occupancy in mitosis. *eLife* 5:4776. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.11402.
- Wilkins BJ, Rall NA, Ostwal Y, Kruitwagen T, Hiragami-Hamada K, Winkler M, Barral Y, Fischle W, Neumann H 2014. A cascade of histone modifications induces chromatin condensation in mitosis. *Science* 343:77–80. DOI: 10.1126/science.1244508.
- Williams BC, Filter JJ, Blake-Hodek KA, Wadzinski BE, Fuda NJ, Shalloway D 2014. Greatwall-phosphorylated Endosulfine is both an inhibitor and a substrate of PP2A-B55 heterotrimer. *eLife* 3:e01695.
- Wittmann T, Wilm M, Karsenti E, Vernos I 2000. TPX2, A novel xenopus MAP involved in spindle pole organization. *Journal of Cell Biology* 149:1405–1418. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.149.7.1405.
- Wolfe BA, Takaki T, Petronczki M, Glotzer M 2009. Polo-Like Kinase 1 Directs Assembly of the HsCdk-4 RhoGAP/Ect2 RhoGEF Complex to Initiate Cleavage Furrow Formation. *PLoS Biology* 7:e1000110. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.1000110.
- Wu JQ, Guo JY, Tang W, Yang C-S, Freil CD, Chen C, Nairn AC, Kornbluth S 2009. PP1-mediated dephosphorylation of phosphoproteins at mitotic exit is controlled by inhibitor-1 and PP1 phosphorylation. *Nature Cell Biology* 11:644–651. DOI: 10.1038/ncb1871.
- Xu Z, Vagnarelli P, Ogawa H, Samejima K, Earnshaw WC 2010. Gradient of increasing Aurora B kinase activity is required for cells to

- execute mitosis. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 285:40163–40170. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M110.181545.
- Yabuta N, Yoshida K, Mukai S, Kato Y, Torigata K, Nojima H 2016. Large tumor suppressors 1 and 2 regulate Aurora-B through phosphorylation of INCENP to ensure completion of cytokinesis. *Heliyon* 2:e00131. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2016.e00131.
- Yamakita Y, Totsukawa G, Yamashiro S, Fry D, Zhang X, Hanks SK, Matsumura F 1999. Dissociation of FAK/p130(CAS)/c-Src complex during mitosis: role of mitosis-specific serine phosphorylation of FAK. *Journal of Cell Biology* 144:315–324. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.144.2.315.
- Yang J, Zappacosta F, Annan RS, Nurse K, Tummino PJ, Copeland RA, Lai Z 2009. The catalytic role of INCENP in Aurora B activation and the kinetic mechanism of Aurora B/INCENP. *The Biochemical journal* 417:355–360. DOI: 10.1042/BJ20081365.
- Yasui Y, Urano T, Kawajiri A, Nagata K-I, Tatsuka M, Saya H, Furukawa K, Takahashi T, Izawa I, Inagaki M 2004. Autophosphorylation of a newly identified site of Aurora-B is indispensable for cytokinesis. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 279:12997–13003. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M311128200.
- Yu Z, Zhou X, Wang W, Deng W, Fang J, Hu H, Wang Z, Li S, Cui L, Shen J, Zhai L, Peng S, Wong J, Dong S, Yuan Z, Ou G, Zhang X, Xu P, Lou J, Yang N, Chen P, Xu R-M, Li G 2015. Dynamic Phosphorylation of CENP-A at Ser68 Orchestrates Its Cell-Cycle-Dependent Deposition at Centromeres. *Developmental Cell* 32:68–81. DOI: 10.1016/j.devcel.2014.11.030.
- Zhang L, Iyer J, Chowdhury A, Ji M, Xiao L, Yang S, Chen Y, Tsai M-Y, Dong J 2012. KIBRA regulates aurora kinase activity and is required for precise chromosome alignment during mitosis. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 287:34069–34077. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M112.385518.
- Zhang S, Chang L, Alfieri C, Zhang Z, Yang J, Maslen S, Skehel M, Barford D 2016. Molecular mechanism of APC/C activation by mitotic phosphorylation. *Nature* 533:260–264. DOI: 10.1038/nature17973.
- Zhou L, Tian X, Zhu C, Wang F, Higgins JMG 2014. Polo-like kinase-1 triggers histone phosphorylation by Haspin in mitosis. *EMBO reports* 15:273–281. DOI: 10.1002/embr.201338080.
- Zorba A, Buosi V, Kutter S, Kern N, Pontiggia F, Cho Y-J, Kern D 2014. Molecular mechanism of Aurora A kinase autophosphorylation and its allosteric activation by TPX2. *eLife* 3:782. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.02667.